

AN EXPLORATION OF THE SPORT AND PHYSICAL
ACTIVITY MOTIVATIONS EXPERIENCED BY PEOPLE
WITH A DISABILITY IN SCOTLAND

By Gemma Lumsdaine

Thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland for the
award of Masters through Research

January 2023

Contents

Acknowledgements	4
Abbreviations	5
Abstract.....	6
Introduction	7
The importance of sport and physical activity on a global scale	7
Participation in the UK.....	7
Health and physical activity participation in Scotland	7
The impact of inequality on Health and engagement in Sport	8
Disability, Sport and Participation in Scotland	9
Literature Review.....	10
Introduction	10
Disability, Sport and Participation	10
Defining Disability	10
Medical model of disability (MMOD)	11
Social model of disability (SMOD)	11
<i>Biopsychosocial Model of Disability (BPSMOD)</i>	13
Assessing Disability	13
<i>International Classification of Function (WHO, 2001)</i>	14
Barriers.....	14
Physical Environmental.....	15
Personal/individual	15
Societal/attitudinal	16
Structural	17
Motivations.....	18
Self-determination Theory (SDT) and PWDParticipation in Sport.....	20
The Importance of Lived Experience	20
Methodology	21
Approach.....	21
Participants	22
Data Collection.....	23
Data Analysis.....	24
Ethical considerations.....	25
Results and Discussion of Findings	26
Demographics	26

Response rate	26
Participant demographics – questionnaire	27
Focus group demographics.....	29
Participant motivations from a numerical perspective	30
Exploring people with disabilities’ motivations for participation from a lived experience perspective	39
Theme 1: “Sport is good for my health” – the physical and mental impact of sports participation	40
<i>Sub Theme: The psychological impact</i>	40
Theme 2: It’s All About the Connections	42
Subtheme: Sports Staff and Coaches.....	43
Subtheme: Community.....	44
Theme 3: psychological factors associated with disability	45
Sub Theme: Changing the Focus.....	46
Overview	47
Recommendations for Practitioners.....	47
Limitations and Future Directions	48
Conclusion.....	49
References	50
Appendices	64
Appendix A – Questionnaire	65
Appendix B- Participant Email and information sheet	83
Appendix C- Interview guide.....	84

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my supervisors Dr Liz Carlin, Professor Gayle McPherson and Professor Richard Davison who have supported, advised, challenged me when needed and most of all believed in me throughout my time at the University of West of Scotland. I would also like to thank the Observatory for Sport in Scotland for funding my studies and always being so enthusiastic about both the wider research project and my thesis. A thanks must also go to my family and friends for being so supportive and encouraging me to do my best. Finally, I would like to thank the research participants for giving up their time to help me complete my project.

Abbreviations

PWD – People with Disabilities

PA- Physical Activity

QOL – Quality of Life

NDP – Non-Disabled People

WHO – World Health Organisation

MMOD – Medical Model of Disability

SMOD – Social Model of Disability

UKSM – UK Social Model

NASM North American Social Model

NSRM -Nordic Social Relational Model

BPSMOD – Biopsychosocial Model of Disability

ICF – International Classification of Function

MH – Mental Health

SDT – Self Determination Theory

ID – Intellectual Disability

Abstract

Participation in sport and physical activity is associated with many physical and mental benefits (Khan et al., 2012), particularly for individuals with a disability (Darcy and Dowse, 2013; Jaarsma et al., 2014a; Jaarsma et al., 2014b). However, despite this, people with disabilities (PWD) in Scotland are significantly less active in comparison to non-disabled people (Scottish Health Survey, 2020). Although a significant amount of research has taken place to explore disability and sports participation, the last research piece on this topic within Scotland took place in 2001 and did not explore people with disabilities' motivations for participation (Suphi et al., 2001). In an attempt to increase awareness of people with disabilities' motivations in relation to sport and inform understanding around participation a mixed method approach was used to research individuals' lived experience. Deci and Ryan's (2002) self-determination theory (SDT) was also applied to provide insight into the motivations of individuals with disabilities who currently participate in sport in Scotland. A questionnaire which explored participant motivations was sent out to a number of disability organisations and disseminated on social media platforms. A total of 450 responses (51 M, 47 F, 1 prefer not to say) were collected from individuals with different disability types (Physical = 403, Intellectual=174, Sight= n29, Hearing =n43, cardio respiratory =n76 Other=n 95) who participate in sport and physical activity at various levels, with the largest number of participants taking part at a recreational level (45% of sample), followed by those competing at a local level (23%). Sport and physical activity type was varied with the most popular activities being walking/pushing activities (14.2%), swimming (12.7%) and gym/weight training (7.5% of sample). The sample age range spanned between 12 and 70. Six online focus groups also took place with a diverse range of participants. Topics covered included perceived benefits and motivations for taking part in sport. Findings suggest that there are a range of factors which influence participant motivations which all link with self-determination theory, these include the physical and psychological impact of participation, the community surrounding disability sport and factors associated with disability such as feelings of acceptance and escapism. Furthermore, disability type can influence the significance of different motivational factors. These discoveries bring new insights around the motivations people experience, particularly in relation to disability type in Scotland. Recommendations include additional training opportunities to develop disability confidence as this can impact individuals' experiences and motivation levels.

Introduction

The importance of sport and physical activity on a global scale

The importance of sport and physical activity is well known with scholars such as Khan et al., (2012) and Easterlin et al., (2019) highlighting the profound physical and mental benefits of taking part in activities such as team sports, walking and cycling for both children (Oberle et al., 2019) and adults (Andersen et al., 2019). Furthermore, engagement in sport can reduce the likelihood of common health issues such as obesity (Lee et al., 2018), cardiac disease (Taylor et al., 2019) and symptoms of depression (Graupensperger et al., 2021). However, despite the positive impact that sport and physical activity can have on individual's health around 80 percent of adolescents spend significant periods of time being inactive (World Health Organisation, 2022a). Furthermore, only one in four adults worldwide meet the current activity guidelines (World Health Organization, 2022a). Given the range of benefits and the influence that participation in sport has on health services capacity levels generally, the World Health Organisation has identified that in order to improve health outcomes, increasing physical activity levels must be a significant priority for countries across the world. To support with this the "Global action plan on physical activity 2018–2030: more active people for a healthier world" was created. This aims to reduce physical inactivity globally by 15 percent by 2030 (World Health Organisation, 2018). In addition to this a number of resources have been created to measure physical activity levels and provide advice on how to get more people active (World Health Organisation, 2022a).

Participation in the UK

Within the UK, participation levels mirror the concerning global statistics. For example, the UK Government state that one in three men are not active enough to experience health benefits. Similarly, one in two women have high levels of inactivity according to UK Government (2022). These figures have significantly worsened since the 1960's (UK Government, 2022), despite an increase in the resources and opportunities available. This is concerning as physical inactivity can result in premature mortality (Heron et al., 2019), which in turn is associated with increased financial demands, and highlights the need to increase activity levels to improve overall health and reduce the strain on national health services (Heron et al., 2019).

Health and physical activity participation in Scotland

Within the context of Scotland, overall health tends to be poorer than in the other home nations (Scottish Government, 2022), with people in Scotland having the shortest life expectancy (Office for National Statistics, 2021; McCartney et al., 2015). For example, statistics suggest that obesity levels in adults are significantly higher in Scotland (30%) (Scottish Health Survey, 2021) compared to

England (28%) (UK Parliament, 2022) and Wales (15%) (National Health Service, Wales, 2022). In addition to poor health outcomes, the Scottish population also has high levels of sedentary behaviour, which includes activities like watching tv and being static, such as spending a considerable time being inactive (Barnes et al., 2012). The Scottish Health Survey (2019) indicates that adults spend an average of 6.2 hours per day being sedentary at the weekend. Furthermore, physical activity rates in Scotland are relatively low with an average of 69 percent of adults meeting the recommended moderate to vigorous physical activity (Scottish Health Survey, 2021). Due to Scotland's poor health outcomes, it could be argued that increasing sports participation is even more of a priority compared to other countries.

The impact of inequality on health and engagement in sport

Despite the correlation between regular sports participation and improved health and wellbeing (Khan et al., 2012; Easterlin et al., 2019), many individuals across the world experience additional barriers and inequalities which negatively impact their health and ability to participate in sport and physical activity (Prestley, 2021). For example, women in the UK are significantly less active than men (Sport England, 2019), this may be due to societal attitudes and perceptions around gender roles (Applebay and Foster, 2013). Furthermore, only 51 percent of adults living in poverty and in the most deprived areas in Scotland, met the physical activity guidelines, compared to 77 percent of people who lived in the least deprived areas (Scottish Health Survey, 2021). Another marginalised group that is disproportionately affected by inequalities, both in their day-to-day life and sporting environments are PWD (Scope, 2022). Data from Sport England's Active Lives Adult Survey (Sport England, 2022) suggests that PWD are twice as likely to be inactive compared to non-disabled people (NDP). This is due to a number of physical, societal and structural barriers such as attitudes around disability, accessibility and cost of participation (Fitzgerald, 2018; Jaarsma et al., 2014b; Martin, 2013).

Low participation rates are problematic as PWD are prone to poor mental wellbeing (Scottish Government, 2017; Jung et al., 2022; Salehi et al. 2015) and are more likely to be affected by health issues (Aherne and Coughlan, 2017). In common with the non-disabled population, sport and physical activity has been shown to promote many physical and psychological benefits (Martin, 2013; Darcy and Dowse, 2013; Jaarsma et al., 2015; Lumsdaine and Lord, 2021) which enhances people with disabilities' quality of life (Yazicioglu et al., 2012; Diaz et al., 2019; Feitosa et al., 2017). Despite a significant amount of research examining participation in sport for PWD (Townsend et al., 2015; Wareham et al., 2017; Bush et al., 2013; McPherson et al., 2016; Wright et al., 2019) it is clear that significant changes need to be made within the UK to increase activity levels, particularly post Covid 19 which has had a massive impact on PWD engagement in sport (Active Alliance 2022; Thesis

et al., 2021).

Disability, Sport and Participation in Scotland

When examining PWD participation in sport and physical activity in Scotland, statistics highlight that less than a quarter of people with a disability take part in sport or physical activity other than walking (or pushing in a wheelchair), compared to nearly a third of non-disabled people living in Scotland (Scottish Health Survey, 2020). However, with the exception of a report published in 2001 by SportsScotland (Suphi et al., 2001) which featured a number of statistics and discussions around the challenges PWD face, individuals' lived experiences, the current landscape and details on the barriers and motivations people experience are relatively unknown within the context of Scotland (Davison and McPherson, 2021). In response to this lack of knowledge and insight on disability, sport and participation, the Observatory for Sport in Scotland and University of the West of Scotland have conducted a large scale research project which aimed to investigate individuals with disabilities experiences in sport within Scotland, identify key motivations and barriers for participation, and map the current landscape and provision available for people with disabilities. As part of this project a study was undertaken to provide additional insight into the motivations of individuals with disabilities. Using data gathered as part of the wider project, this research aims to gain knowledge and understanding of the motivations of PWD who currently participate in sport in Scotland.

In addition to the aim, the project has four objectives; firstly, to explore the relationship between self-determination theory and sports participation for PWD in Scotland, secondly, to explore potential similarities and differences in the motivations of people with different disability types, thirdly, to provide recommendations for future research in this area, and finally to provide practical recommendations on how to enhance the motivation levels of PWD for those working in the sports industry.

This thesis will begin with a literature review that explores the complexities of sport participation and disability to help provide contextual information and insights from within this field of study. This will be followed by an overview of the methodology utilised within this study. The results of both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of this project will then be presented and discussed in depth. Finally, this thesis will finish with a conclusion and recommendations for future research and guidance for sports practitioners.

Literature Review

Introduction

The field of disability and sport has been of growing interest to academics in recent years, for example, coaching practices (Townsend et al., 2015; Wareham et al., 2017) media representation of paralympic athletes (Bush et al., 2013; McPherson et al., 2016) and children with disabilities' experiences of sport (Wright et al., 2019) have all been popular topics. However, there has been a lack of research examining people with disabilities' experiences within sport particularly within Scotland (Davison and McPherson, 2021). The following section of this report will focus on the motivations of PWD(PWD) in relation to physical activity and sport participation in Scotland. The complexities associated with disability and sports participation are significant due to the influence this has on the perceptions of disability within society and the associated link with sporting opportunities for PWD (Smith and Bundon, 2018). These factors are explored within this literature review.

Disability, Sport and Participation

Participation in sport has been associated with many physical, mental and social benefits (Khan et al., 2012), particularly for PWD (Darcy and Dowse, 2013; Stephens et al., 2012). However, despite this the Scottish Health Survey (2020) suggests that only 23 percent of people with a disability take part in sport or physical activity that does not involve walking, compared to 31 percent of non-disabled people in Scotland. Furthermore, PWD have poorer psychological wellbeing in comparison to non-disabled people (Scottish Government, 2017). These statistics highlight the need to explore issues around disability and sport with a view to identifying the positive and negative factors that influence whether PWD participate in sport. Furthermore, it could be argued that increasing participation levels is a priority for the sport, physical activity and health sector due to the correlation between sport and physical activity participation and quality of life (QOL) for PWD (Yazicioglu et al., 2012; Diaz et al., 2019; Feitosa et al., 2017).

Defining Disability

In recent years the definition and concept of disability has become a popular topic amongst many disability sport scholars (Fitzgerald, 2012; Brighton et al., 2021), as the way society views and understands disability has direct implications for sport and physical activity participation for PWD (Smith and Bundon, 2018). There are a number of models which try to conceptualize disability. Within this thesis three key models of disability are outlined to explain the contextual background surrounding disability.

Medical model of disability (MMOD)

The medical model of disability was created from a medical perspective (Petasis, 2019) and views an individual's impairment as the issue. This model defines disability as any lack of function or ability to do something to the same extent or in the same way as a normal person due to impairment (Goodley and Swartz, 2016). Furthermore, this perspective tends to focus on ways to "fix" or "heal" PWD (Goering, 2015; Cottingham et al., 2018) which then allows them to fit into society. The MMOD emphasises that it is the individual's body itself which is the problem (Haegle and Hodge, 2016). However, this point of view is problematic as it fails to acknowledge a range of societal and attitudinal factors which can prevent individuals from being able to engage within our society (Goodley, 2012). In addition, using the phrase "normal", which is a socially constructed term, to determine what is and isn't disability implies that nondisabled people are "normal", superior and more valued whereas PWD are different, inferior and inadequate (Haslett and Smith, 2020). This subtle but impactful narrative around supremacy and able-bodied hegemony can create further inequality and prejudice within society which may result in PWD having to experience even more barriers and challenges.

Social model of disability (SMOD)

As a result of frustration and criticism of the medical model, PWD who were involved in campaigning for human rights created the UK social model of disability (Smith and Bundon, 2018). In contrast to the medical model of disability, the UK social model of disability suggests that societal barriers (attitudinal, physical and environmental) cause disability (Oliver, 2013), as these barriers prevent PWD from participating in activities, getting jobs, and engaging in society not the individual's impairment itself (Oliver, 2013).

The creation of this model has supported individuals with disabilities to challenge discrimination and fight for improved access and opportunities (Oliver, 2013; Owens, 2015). However, despite this positive move towards inclusion and equality, many scholars and organisations have criticized the social model of disability for many reasons (Owens, 2015; Barnes, 2012). Firstly, the UK Social Model of Disability categorises all individuals with a disability into one group where everyone has the same needs, challenges and experiences. However, there are many factors which influence individuals' opportunities with society such as race, gender, age and socioeconomic status which the social model does not consider (Dyson and Berghs, 2019; Oliver, 2017). For example, when examining intersectionalities such as disability and gender, women with disabilities experience a number of different challenges which are associated with both their gender and disability and the interaction between these two characteristics (Hums, 2016). This highlights how different characteristics can be interlinked and influence individuals' experiences and opportunities, which is a factor that the social

model of disability does not recognise or take into account. Scholars have also suggested that this model fails to acknowledge and understand the challenges PWD experience due to their impairment, (Degener, 2017) such as pain and fatigue which cannot be solved by simply changing attitudes of non-disabled people (Oliver, 2017; Goering, 2015) or adding ramp access to a building. This emphasises how the social model does not consider a range of factors which impact people with disabilities' day to day life.

Various countries across the world have acknowledged the critiques of the UK Social model and have adapted the model (Haslett and Smith, 2020) to address criticisms and reflect cultural differences. For example, the Nordic Social Relative Model (NSRM) was created to establish an alternative definition and understanding of disability, which in contrast to the UK Social Model (UKSM) recognises the complex interaction between disability and impairment (Riddle, 2013) and encompasses individual' lived experience (Mallett and Runswick-Cole 2014). Furthermore, this model identifies that disability is multifaceted, situational, and relative depending on the environment an individual finds themselves in (Goodley and Swartz, 2016). Finally, the NSRM argues that disability is experienced when an individual with an impairment interacts with inaccessibility (physical, social and structural) within society (Goodley, 2011). This builds upon ideas from the UK social model but also acknowledges the wider challenges that PWD face.

Disability theorists in North America also looked to conceptualise disability and as a result created the North American social model, commonly known as the minority model. This framework is similar to both UK and Nordic Social model as it also recognises that societal factors e.g. attitudes of others can cause disability (Haslett and Smith, 2020). However, the minority model differs from the other models as it makes a comparison between PWD experiences and other minority groups such as those from ethnically diverse communities, (Fredrick and Shifer, 2019), particularly the similarities between able bodied hegemony and white privilege (Goodley and Swartz, 2016). Furthermore, this model's definition of disability suggests that disability is experienced as a result of society failing to meet the needs of individuals with a disability (Smith and Bundon, 2018). The aim of this definition was to put more political pressure on government to be more inclusive and demand a more inclusive culture. However, similarly to the UK Social Model the minority model has received criticism that it suggests disability is purely created by society which disregards the physical and environmental barriers that individuals face as a result of their impairment (Anastasiou and Kauffman, 2012). Despite the multiple versions of the Social Model of Disability it is apparent that the key concepts within the model are widely contested and often too simplistic which prevents this model from providing a relevant and representative understanding of disability (Anastasiou and Kauffman, 2012).

Biopsychosocial Model of Disability (BPSMOD)

The Biopsychosocial Model of Disability was established in the 1970's in an attempt to combine approaches from both the medical and social model of disability (Bath et al., 2014) and to address the critiques which are outlined above (Petasis, 2019). This model suggests that disability can be defined as the interaction between three factors: physical, such as an individual's functional ability, psychological e.g. behaviour and social such as cultural/ societal influences (Bath et al., 2014). Furthermore, the Biopsychosocial model of disability highlights that barriers and discrimination for PWD are caused by both societal factors such as negative attitudes and individual limitations as a result of impairment. More recently the original model by George Engles has been further developed by Waddel and Aylesward to create a more multifaceted perspective of disability which incorporates aspects such as whether individuals are receiving professional care or social modifications, and a person's effort levels (Shakespeare et al., 2016). This evolution has supported the government to implement support mechanisms and policies to enable more PWD to access employment (Shakespeare et al., 2016). However, this hasn't been without criticism, scholars suggest that despite the progress that this model has made in relation to policy and support mechanisms, there has not been a significant increase in the number of disabled people employed. Furthermore, the BPSMOD based criteria that has been adopted to determine individuals support requirements limits the number of PWD who can receive employment support (Shakespeare et al., 2017). Disability critics have also suggested that the individual's effort dimension of the model aligns with ableist and medical model perspectives by putting the onus on the individual rather than acknowledging the oppression which impacts on a number of factors in a person life e.g. employment status. This lack of recognition contradicts and undermines the social element of this model (Adams et al., 2019). It is apparent that this model has conceptualised disability in a way that is multifaceted and not one dimensional which has in turn created changes within government and the support systems they provide. However, it is clear that there are a number of criticisms that need be addressed, particularly in relation to the practical application of this model within multiple sectors in order to create positive and meaningful change for people with disabilities.

Assessing Disability

Measuring disability and impairment is important for several reasons. Firstly, the measurement of functional ability and impairment helps government services such as social work identify the amount and type of support individuals need. (Palmer and Hartley, 2012). Secondly, by measuring the impact and prevalence of disability within a population, policy makers are made aware of the challenges PWD face and can therefore create policy which aims to address these challenges (Palmer and Hartley, 2012). Finally, it could be argued that having a framework such as the ICF (WHO, 2001)

enables organisations, practitioners and policy makers to have a more coherent and established definition and understanding of disability (Smith and Bundon, 2017) which may result in more consistent assessment of disability.

International Classification of Function (WHO, 2001)

One method to measure disability and impairment is by using the World Health Organisations International Classification of Function (ICF) (WHO, 2001) which is an in-depth framework that measures individuals' functional ability and how this influences their day-to-day life. The ICF implements key concepts from the biopsychosocial model of disability (Petasis, 2019) such as assessing environmental and societal factors as well as physical function.

A strength of the ICF is its ability to explore individual's physical function, challenges, and barriers. This data can then be used to help identify the challenges individuals with a disability face both within day-to-day life (Gallagher et al., 2011) and when trying to access sport and physical activity (Mulligan et al., 2012) which can improve our understanding of PWD experiences. This could contribute to improvements or increased support to overcome the barriers PWD experience when trying to engage in sport (Mulligan et al., 2012) and society in general (Gallagher et al., 2011). As evidenced above the ICF has been used within the field to understand individuals function and how this influences their experience. Despite this data and insight that has been collected, it is still unknown is how the different ICF components e.g. personal factors, physical function etc interact with each other. This limits scholars overall understanding of individuals' experiences of living with a disability (Heerkens et al., 2018). Furthermore, the ICF (WHO, 2001) has not been utilised in Scotland to understand people with disabilities' experiences in day-to-day life or within sport which highlights a significant gap in the field (Davison and McPherson, 2021).

Barriers

In an attempt to understand and address PWD low participation rates scholars have investigated the barriers which prevent PWD from taking part in sport (Martin, 2013; Jaarsma et al., 2014a Jaarsma et al., 2014b). Within this thesis a barrier can be defined as anything that stops or impedes individuals with a disability engaging in sport or physical activity (McLoughlin et al., 2017).

To aid analysis and understanding, barriers to sport and physical activity participation are split into four broad categories: physical environmental, societal/attitudinal, personal and structural, which are adapted from work by Van Schijndel-speet et al., (2014).

Physical Environmental

Physical environmental factors such as inaccessible sports facilities and difficulties with transport prevent PWD from participating in sport and physical activity (Jaarsma et al., 2014b; Martin, 2013). For example, it has been established that physical barriers within the sports industry such as equipment needing to be operated by staff and not by the individuals themselves decreases autonomy and choice during exercise (Rolfe et al., 2012). Furthermore, the inaccessible nature of public transport has been identified as a significant barrier to participation (Smith et al., 2016; Fitzgerald 2018), for example the lack of regular accessible busses has been shown to prevent people from attending sport and physical activity sessions, this lack of appropriate provision removes the element of choice and ability to be flexible which can then reduce feelings of autonomy (Pyer and Tucker 2017). Due to the correlation between autonomy and motivation (Ryan and Deci, 2017) it could be argued that the physical barriers decrease autonomy and therefore motivation to participate in sport. However, this correlation between barriers, autonomy and motivation has not been explored within Scotland which highlights a significant gap in our understanding of this topic.

Personal/individual

Within this thesis a personal barrier, sometimes referred to as an individual barrier (Jaarsma et al., 2014b) can be defined as a factor which relates to the individual themselves rather than an external or social influence. Many scholars suggest that one of the biggest individual barriers which prevent PWD participating in sport is their disability itself (Jaarsma et al., 2014b; Jaarsma et al., 2015). One explanation for this finding may be due to the link between disability and low levels of self-concept and confidence (Patterson et al., 2012,). For example, individuals with disabilities have lower self-esteem and confidence due to their perceptions around being less physically able (Patterson et al., 2012; Brittan et al., 2020) which in turn impacts upon their motivation to participate. This could be linked to internalised ableism (Brittan et al., 2020) and low levels of self-efficacy (Bandura, 1977) which can influence participation. It could be argued that low levels of self-efficacy are linked to a lack of representation of disabled people participating in sport at grassroots level. For example, currently the main source of representation for participation in sport for PWD is the Paralympics. However, many people within the disabled community struggle to relate to Paralympians or see themselves being able to perform a skill that paralympic athletes have mastered (Brown and Pappous, 2018). This may result in a less positive vicarious experience (seeing another individual take part in activity or task), which can impact upon self-efficacy levels (Bandura, 2006; Shipherd et al., 2021) and potential likelihood to engage in sport (Bandura 1977). Arguably, another explanation for this finding could be the correlation between low confidence and lack of motivation to participate in sport and physical activity (Deci and Ryan, 2017). However, the link between disability

and participation has not been established consistently throughout the literature (Jaarsma et al., 2014b), which suggests that this needs to be explored further, particularly examining psychological factors e.g. motivation and how this influences individuals engagement in sport and physical activity.

Caton et al., (2012) and Aherne and Coughlan (2017) suggest that health issues such as heart problems and obesity are significant barriers for individuals with intellectual disabilities when participating in sport. This finding emphasises that engagement in sport is complex and interlinked with a variety of different factors which need to be addressed to enable participation. In addition to health and disability, lack of support can result in PWD disengaging from sport and physical activity participation (Martin et al., 2016). For example, Hansen et al., (2021) explored the barriers and facilitators to sports participation for individuals with intellectual disabilities. Findings suggested that a lack of support from parents, teachers, friends and coaches negatively impacted their experiences of sport and physical activity and prevented them being active. This highlights the important role that family, friends and professionals have in shaping individuals' experiences of sport (Banack et al., 2011), and therefore subsequent involvement in sport and physical activity. This links to ideas around psychological needs which suggest that if individuals develop positive relationships with coaches, teammates etc this can create a greater sense of belonging which increases motivation and supports continued engagement (Ryan and Deci, 2017). A limitation of Banack et al., (2011)'s study however, is that it only explored people with intellectual disabilities experiences which highlights a potential gap in knowledge around the impact of support on people with other disabilities participation experiences and motivation.

Lack of confidence (Stephens et al., 2012; Shields et al., 2012; Van Schijndel-speet et al., 2014; Deans et al., 2012), self-consciousness (Newitt et al., 2016) and negative self-comparison to non-disabled people (Shields and Synott, 2016) are significant barriers to participation. It could be argued that these barriers stem from ableism, which is a form of prejudice that views nondisabled people as "normal" and superior within our society (Smith et al., 2021). This may help to explain individuals lack confidence due to feeling inferior and undervalued in comparison to their nondisabled peers. In addition, this is an important finding in relation to sports participation as one of the key factors that influence whether individuals participate in sport is high levels confidence, and feelings of competence (Ryan and Deci, 2017). However, it is currently unknown how confidence influences PWD motivation to engage in sport and physical activity in Scotland.

Societal/attitudinal

Historically, society has portrayed PWD as tragedies and objects of pity (Martin, 2013; Fitzgerald, 2018). These perceptions and negative attitudes which often do not recognise the abilities of PWD

or view individuals as inspirational for doing mundane tasks (Martin, 2013) have filtered into sporting environments and can have a significant impact on individuals experiences and engagement in sport and physical activity (Smith and Sparkes, 2019; Jaarsma et al., 2014a; Fitzgerald, 2018; Darcy and Dowse, 2013). For example, Shields and Synott (2016) examined the barriers children with disabilities experience when participating in sport and physical activity by facilitating focus groups for children aged 10-18 with a disability, parents of children with a disability and individuals working within the sector such as coaches and sports development officers. Within this research all three participant groups (children, parents and sports staff) emphasised that negative attitudes around disability was the most significant barrier to participation in sport and physical activity. These findings highlight the influence and significance that individual and societal attitudes can have on PWD participation in sport and physical activity, particularly, individuals' motivation levels as by experiencing constant negativity about their disability may subsequently reinforce internal ableism which manifests as not feeling capable of taking part in sport, this may result in individuals stopping taking part in sport (Brittian et al., 2020). This may suggest the need to focus on changing attitudes around disability in order to increase participation and create more positive experiences which may help increase individuals' motivation to engage in sport and physical activity. However, it is currently unclear how the attitudes of those facilitating participation e.g. coaches influence individuals' motivation to take part in sport within Scotland which highlights a significant gap within our understanding of this area. Closely linked to negative attitudes is a lack of knowledge and understanding of disability which has also been found to prevent individuals from taking part or continuing to participate in sport (Darcy and Dowse 2013; Fitzgerald, 2018; Ginis et al., 2021). For example, teachers or coaches being unaware of how to adapt activities to suit the needs of individuals can result in PWD disengaging in sport (Shields and Synott, 2016). These finding suggests a correlation between coaches' knowledge, attitude and participant experiences. Furthermore, it could be argued that by enhancing the sports industry personnel's knowledge and understanding around how to adapt sessions and include people with a variety of different disabilities participants experience higher levels of self-efficacy due to the connection between positive interactions with coaches and self-efficacy (Weight et al., 2020), from a self determination perspective, individuals could feel more motivated due to greater feelings of relatedness with coaches as a result of them having an increased understanding of how to accommodate their needs within a sporting setting (Deci and Ryan, 2017).

Structural

PWD face structural inequalities and barriers in every aspect of life, such as limited opportunities to gain educational qualifications (Ahmad, 2012) and significantly lower employment rates in

comparison to non-disabled people (UK Parliament, 2021). These differences stem from various organisational and societal structures being designed for and in favour of non-disabled people, as sport reflects society and society reflects sport this is often the case in sport and physical activity spaces too (Fitzgerald, 2018).

Furthermore, structural barriers such as limited opportunities (Haslett et al., 2017), lack of competitions and costs associated with participation (McLoughlin et al., 2017; Ives et al., 2021; Newitt et al., 2016; Darcy and Dowse, 2013; Ginis et al., 2021) significantly effect individuals ability to engage in sport and physical activity. In addition to the cost of participation, socioeconomic status (Ginis et al., 2021) which is a combination of three indicators, educational qualifications, income and occupation (Lam et al., 2019) has been shown to have a significant impact on PWD participation in sport and physical activity (Rimmer and Rowland, 2008; Mascarinas and Blauwett, 2018; Ginis et al., 2021). Many individuals with a disability experience barriers to education (Amhad, 2012; Lindsay et al., 2018) which then leads to unemployment and poverty (Abidi and Sharma, 2014). Davison and McPherson (2021) highlight that data within the Scottish Health Survey (2018) suggests that poverty and deprivation negatively impacts PWD participation in sport, this may be due to the impact of poverty and disability on individuals' autonomy (Burchardt et al., 2015), which is a key factor in behaviour adherence (Deci and Ryan, 2002). For example, PWD who are experiencing poverty may not have a choice in what activities they can engage in due to financial constraints, this lack of choice and opportunities may demotivate individuals. Furthermore, people experiencing poverty often avoid trying new activities such as sports clubs due to a lack of confidence (Vandermeerschen et al., 2017) which may help to explain low participation rates as feelings of confidence are often linked with increased motivation to be active (Bloemen et al., 2015; Ives et al., 2021). These findings highlight that the combination of having a disability and living in poverty creates significant challenges in terms of sports participation which may influence motivation levels for PWD living in Scotland.

Motivations

Despite the many barriers that PWD experience both within everyday life and within a sporting context, many are still motivated to participate and often have similar motivations for taking part in sport and physical activity as non-disabled people (McLoughlin et al., 2017). For example, Kampfe et al., (2014) found that both non-disabled people and PWD engage in sport for enjoyment, skill development and the socialization with others. These findings may have a correlation with to a number of motivational theories, for example individuals who are motivated by internal factors such as improving a certain skill tend to have a higher level of intrinsic motivation (Nicholls, 1984) which has been shown to have a significant impact on continued engagement in sport (Gardener et al.,

2017). Furthermore, findings around enjoyment and socialization link to the idea that if an individual feels connected and part of a group they'll continue to engage in that activity or behaviour (Deci and Ryan, 2000). In addition, Jaarsma et al., (2014a), Mcloughlin et al., (2017) and Darcey and Dowse (2013) state that competition and being competitive is a big motivator for people with disabilities.

Individuals with disabilities also have unique motives for participating and staying involved in sport which differ to non-disabled people's motivations. For example, Stephens et al., (2012) explored individuals with a Spinal Cord Injury experiences of disability sport and their motivations behind participation. Findings suggested that a key reason people participate in sport was to socialise with other people who had similar disabilities. As a result of this socialisation individuals learned life skills, improved their independence and increased their self-worth, which is often lower in PWD (Reel and Bucciere, 2010). These findings highlight the significance of socialising with others who have similar disabilities and the positive impact that this has on both mental and physical health. It could be argued that increased self-efficacy particularly through vicarious experiences (Bandura, 1977), such as individuals seeing other people with similar disabilities completing daily tasks e.g. transferring from one wheelchair to another increases an individual's belief in their own ability to perform this task, which may have contributed to higher levels of independence and greater feelings of self-worth as a result of achieving these milestones. In addition, these research findings suggest a link between relatedness, self-worth and continued participation in sport.

Various studies have examined the motivations of people with different types of disabilities (Jaarsma et al., 2014a; Mcloughlin et al., 2017; Jaarsma et al., 2016; Van Schijndel-speet et al., 2014). Scholars suggest that people with physical (McLoughlin et al., 2017), sensory (Jaarsma et al., 2014a), and intellectual disabilities (Hansen et al., 2021; Darcy and Dowse, 2013) all participate in sport for fun and enjoyment. This research highlights similarities in the motivations of people with a variety of different disability types. Despite these findings, it is difficult to know whether there are differences in the motivations of people with different types of impairment as limited research, particularly within Scotland has compared the motivations of people with different disabilities experience e.g. visual impairment compared to physical disability (Davison and McPherson, 2021). This is an important gap which needs to be addressed as having an understanding of the similarities and differences in motivations that different impairment groups experience would enable professionals and organisations to use the specific and relevant methods to target impairment groups based on their motivations which in turn may help to improve the low participation rates for PWD within Scotland (Scottish Health Survey, 2020).

Self Determination Theory and People with Disabilities Participation in Sport

In recent years Self Determination Theory has become an increasingly popular approach to understand engagement in physical education (White et al., 2021) and motivation in sport and physical activity both for non-disabled people (Hancox et al., 2018 Ntoumanis et al., 2017; Tsai et al., 2021) and PWD (Bentzen et al., 2022; Bremer et al., 2023). This theory suggests that motivation is a continuum which has amotivation, where individuals have no desire to participate at one end and intrinsic motivation, where individuals engage in an activity due to enjoyment and interest in the activity at the opposite end of the spectrum.

Figure 1: A diagram of self-determination theory, which highlights that each psychological need contributes to increased intrinsic motivation

In addition to motivation levels this theory identifies that individuals have three basic psychological needs (see figure 1); relatedness, which refers to an individual having a sense of belonging and feeling connected to others, autonomy, which suggests individuals feel in control of their own decisions and choices and finally competency, which can be described as a person's confidence in their own ability to achieve a task or goal.

Deci and Ryan (2002) suggest that if these needs are met individuals will develop intrinsic motivation, which will result in continued engagement in physical activity and sport (Ryan and Deci, 2017). This theory has been selected and purposefully developed for this thesis as it is a more holistic approach (Roberts and Walker, 2020) which unlike other motivational theories such as achievement goal theory takes into account social and cultural influences (Alfermann, 2016). This is an important factor when exploring motivations and disability, due to the complex and multifaceted

nature of disability and participation in sport (Smith and Bundon, 2018). Furthermore, based upon previous literature which suggests individuals with disabilities experience a greater sense of self-worth, increased independence and feelings of connectedness as a result of participating in sport and physical activity (Stephens et al., 2012; McCarty et al., 2022) it is clear that there is a connection between sport and physical activity engagement, motivation and the psychological needs outlined in self-determination theory (Deci and Ryan, 2002). However, despite this correlation and the growing body of literature which explores motivations, particularly using SDT and disability, the current literature tends to focus on disability and physical activity within a clinical setting such as rehab centres (Saebu et al., 2013) or elite athletes (McLoughlin et al., 2017; Ballas et al., 2020), very little research has examined PWD motivations for engaging in sport in Scotland (Davison and McPherson, 2021), particularly with a focus on whether these motivations are linked to the psychological needs described in Self Determination Theory.

The objectives of this project are to explore the relationship between self-determination theory and sports participation for people with a disability in Scotland, to examine potential similarities and differences in motivations of people with different disability types, to provide recommendations for future research in this area and to suggest practical recommendations around how to enhance the motivation levels of PWD for those working in the sports industry.

Methodology

This section outlines the methodological approaches utilised within this research, both in terms of the wider University of the West of Scotland and Observatory for Sport in Scotland project, and the analysis undertaken specifically around the motivation of individuals with a disability who currently engage in sport and activity in Scotland.

Approach

This research utilised a mixed method approach to explore the motivations associated with sports participation in a sample group comprising of people who identified as having a disability. This study works within an interpretivism paradigm (Smith et al., 2017; Atkinson, 2012) which identifies that knowledge is subjective, socially constructed and can depend on individual and societal interactions (Potrac et al., 2014). Therefore, in order to gain a greater understanding of PWD motivations for participation, individuals' thoughts, experiences and feelings (Coe, 2012) have been explored.

Participants

Criterion sampling, which allows researchers to recruit participants with the most relevant experience (Sparkes and Smith, 2014) was used to recruit participants for both the quantitative (questionnaire) and qualitative (Focus Group) data collection phases of this research. The criteria for participating in this research included three key factors; Individuals had to have a disability (physical, sensory, or intellectual), be between the ages of 12 and 70 and currently live in Scotland.

Participants with a disability were selected as this allowed the researcher to gain insight into the experiences of people with disabilities, which can be used to increase understanding around the motivations that individuals with a disability experience when trying to access sport and physical activity, this information can then help to shape policy and provision. The lower age limit was selected to allow the researchers to explore young peoples' experiences of sport, in particular physical education. Therefore, by having participants aged 12 and above data can be gathered about individual's experiences of primary and secondary physical education. The upper age limit was chosen due to the prevalence of people over the age of 70 developing other health difficulties such as cognitive impairment and loss of mobility as a result of old age (Melzer et al., 2015; WHO, 2022b). Although these conditions can result in disability it may have affected the accuracy and relevance of the data collected due to differences between people who have acquired disability as a result of old age or those who have a congenital or acquired disability caused by different factors. In addition to participant age, participant location has also been considered and people who currently live in Scotland have been chosen as this research specifically explored the motivations of PWD who are currently participating in sport and physical activity within Scotland. Finally, the decision to collect data on biological sex rather than gender was made to ensure that the demographic questions asked within this study mirrored other Scottish surveys (Scottish Government, 2021), which enabled a standardised approach to be adopted.

Recruitment

Once ethical approval was granted the questionnaire (Appendix A) and participant information sheet (Appendix B) was disseminated via email to key disability groups who have large memberships and connections within the disabled community in Scotland. These groups included both sports specific organisations such as Scottish Disability Sport and general disability organisations, for example Disability Equality Scotland who support individuals with a wide range of disabilities. The questionnaire was also promoted on multiple social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn.

At the end of the questionnaire participants were asked if they were happy to participate in a follow up focus group to explore their experiences further. If the participant agreed to be involved, they

could input their contact details. A follow up email was then sent out to participants which included focus group meeting details, dates and times. Information was also shared with disability organisations and on social media. Accessibility considerations were adopted throughout this process, for example, image descriptions were added to social media to allow individuals with a visual impairment to engage with content, language was simplified where possible to ensure the content could be accessed by people with an intellectual disability and a video was created with British Sign Language and captions to ensure adverts were accessible to people with a hearing impairment.

Data Collection

Quantitative

Quantitative data on participant motivations were collected using a in depth questionnaire which was conducted on Question Pro (Appendix A). Four key sections were included within the questionnaire; Sport and Physical Activity, Physical Function which was based upon the ICF Checklist (WHO, 2001), Support and Demographics which were taken directly from the Scottish Household Survey (2019). Questions around motivation were developed from key theoretical concepts from SDT such as *“Why do you take part in sport/physical activity (Please select all that apply)?”* this question looked to explore whether motivations were related to psychological needs and/or intrinsic motivation for example if responses were, making new friends and being part of a team, which links to relatedness. Furthermore, the following question *“Since participating in sport and physical activity have you experienced any of the following benefits?”* examined whether psychological needs had been met as a result of participating in sport and physical activity, such as increased confidence and self-esteem which may suggest increased feelings of competency.

Qualitative

Insight into individuals’ experiences were collected through the facilitation of six online semi structured focus groups. This form of data collection was selected as it allows multiple participants to share their experiences and interact with each other (Sparkes and Smith, 2013). This helped the conversation flow and enabled a more participant led discussion (Sparkes and Smith, 2013). In addition, online focus groups were selected to try and remove travel barriers which often prevent PWD engaging in activities (Bezyak et al., 2020). Accessibility factors were also taken into consideration, for example, British Sign Language interpreters were present during a number of sessions, participants were made aware of which sessions had a BSL interpreter in attendance on Eventbrite where individuals signed up for the focus groups. In addition, regular eye breaks were also given to allow participants and British Sign Language interpreters to have a break from the screen. Additional time was factored into the focus groups to ensure individuals had enough time to

process and contribute to discussions. Finally, prompts were simplified if required and information around topics were provided in advance to give participants additional time to familiarise themselves with the topics and questions. The interviews focused on four key areas which influence participation, these included social factors such as the attitudes of others, physical factors, e.g experiences around transport and accessibility, psychological factors such as participation motivations which were informed by survey responses and structured to explore whether motivations were intrinsic and connected to key theoretical concepts. Stressors and sport specific factors which focused on individuals experiences within their chosen sport or physical activity were also covered as part of the wider research project.

At the beginning of the focus group information around informed consent was given and participants were asked if they consent to the discussion being recorded for analysis purposes. The researcher then introduced the research and used a question guide to prompt discussion (Appendix C), however flexibility to expand, delve deeper or discuss alternative topics was embedded throughout.

Data Analysis

Qualitative data was first transcribed using the transcription programme Otter Artificial Intelligence, during this process the transcriptions were checked for accuracy. Once the transcripts were complete, thematic analysis (Braun et al., 2016) was used to analyse the data. This method was selected as it enables key themes and patterns to be identified within the data (Braun et al., 2016) and is often used within disability sport research (Alan et al., 2020; Jesus et al., 2021; Ballas et al., 2020) to gain a greater insight into individuals lived experience and explore the most prominent factors within individuals' lives.

Braun and Clarke's 6 step framework (Braun and Clarke, 2006) was used to perform the analysis. The initial phase "immersion" involved listening to the recordings and reading the transcripts to gain familiarity with the data. Following this, stage two and three of the framework, which involved initial coding and identify themes and patterns within the data were combined (see appendix D for thematic analysis table). Four themes were then reviewed and named based upon their topic, sub themes were also created at this stage to help breakdown and simplify larger themes within the data (See Appendix E) (Sparkes and Smith, 2013). Finally, the key themes and findings were reported in the researcher's thesis. Data was presented with a high participants voice (Pittney and Parker, 2009) to ensure individuals lived experience was represented throughout. This was achieved by using realist tales to illustrate and emphasise findings (Sparkes and Smith, 2013; King, 2016).

Participant demographics including age breakdown, gender, participation level, of participants were analysed using basic statistical tests such as frequency distribution, standard deviation and percentage breakdown on SPSS software.

Ethical considerations

Within this thesis a number of ethical factors were considered to ensure that the research was conducted in an ethical manor and that both the researcher and the participants were safe. Several risks were discussed and mitigated by putting a number of procedures in place.

Informed Consent and Capacity

Gaining written consent from participants who take part in the project is a vital element of this type of research to ensure ethical practice is followed (Sparkes Smith, 2014). As a result of this, participants were asked to fill out a section on consent at the beginning of the questionnaire. The survey was also programmed to ensure individuals could not begin the questionnaire without giving consent.

Due to the increased vulnerability and nature of the groups we were working, particularly those with intellectual disabilities, extra thought had to be taken in relation to consent and capacity to complete the questionnaire. After discussions with experts in the field, it was decided that additional consent questions would be added to ensure the survey was accessible to those under 18 requiring parental consent, or those who lack capacity or functioning to complete the survey, thus allowing completion by proxy. These additional statements were guided by The Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000 which outlines that research on adults incapable of consenting is authorized under several circumstances. Such conditions include; when the research entails little or no risk or discomfort, the person is not objecting, and that consent has been obtained from a person with relevant powers. Consent may be obtained from a legal guardian or nearest relative if no one has been appointed.

Prior to research commencing, participants and national disability organisations were sent a participant information sheet (Appendix B) which included key information on confidentiality, consent and the right to withdraw from the project at any point. The participants were reminded again during the study that their engagement is optional and that they have the right to withdraw at any point (Sparkes, Smith, 2014). In addition, participants could skip any questions in the questionnaire that made them feel uncomfortable. Furthermore, at the beginning of the focus groups participants were reminded that they did not need to discuss anything that caused them to be distressed. Throughout the focus group the researcher tried to create a relaxed and informal atmosphere to reassure those who were attending the focus groups.

Anonymity and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

To protect participants' identities and personal information, pseudonyms were used throughout the qualitative section of this research. For example, during transcription, data analysis and data presentation. The questionnaire did not ask for personal identifiers such as names. The option was given to provide a contact email address for a follow up interview, however, this was not mandatory. Participants personal information and data was stored into a secure location (University M Drive) on a password protected laptop.

Online Interview Environment

As the qualitative data collection took place online via Microsoft Teams there were some ethical considerations which needed to be addressed. For example, unlike face-to-face interviews there isn't the opportunity for participants to fill out the consent form at the time of the interview. Participants were reminded about informed consent and asked if they consent to the interviewed being recorded for audio purposes only. This was recorded on Teams for documentation purposes.

Results and Discussion of Findings

The results of the study are set out below with general demographics being outlined, qualitative and quantitative findings are then split into two sub-sections which include discussion around the data collected for each research approach used within this project. Data analysis from the questionnaire around participants motivations for taking part in sport and physical activity will then be presented and discussed, comparisons will also be made based upon individuals age and disability type to identify any common similarities or differences between groups.

Demographics

This section will outline participant demographics such as age, disability type and sex from both the questionnaire and focus group to provide contextual information about the research participants involved in this study.

Response rate

A total of 450 completed responses were received from the questionnaire, with 12.1% of responses being from PWD who do not currently participate in sport or physical activity (N=70) which suggests a significant disparity in terms of those who are currently participating compared to those who are inactive. This may be due to inactive individuals thinking that sport and physical activity is not of value or a priority for them which results in them avoiding engagement in research involving sport and physical activity.

Participant demographics – questionnaire

Age

Age Range	Number of participants
12-15	35
16-24	51
25-32	39
33-40	31
41-48	16
49-55	31
56-64	43
65-70	15

Table 1: Participant age range

Participants ages ranged from 12 to 70 with all age groups being represented within the questionnaire. The largest number of responses was from the age 16-24 age group and the smallest from the 65-70 age range. The results within this figure are mainly representative of the Scottish population apart from the 16-24 category which is slightly overrepresented and the 41 – 48 category which is slightly underrepresented (Scottish Health Survey, 2019). This suggests that there may be more opportunities to participate in sport for young PWD compared to middle aged to older adults with disabilities in Scotland (Davison et.al., under review) and could potentially highlight some differences in terms of challenges related to other time limiting factors for example work or further education.

Disability type - questionnaire

The section below will outline the breakdown of respondent's disability type within the questionnaire. This is significant as one of the objectives of this project is to identify differences and similarities between different disability groups. Therefore, it is important to have a more general understanding of the disability breakdown and associated trends within this study as this will allow analysis to be more accurate and relevant.

Figure 2: Number of participants and disability type

The respondents disability type is presented in figure two. Disability was categorised in terms of the primary impact of impairment on the individual’s day to day function. From this sub-category were created to better highlight traditional disability groups. The figure above indicates that the questionnaire was primarily completed by those with a physical disability. Due to the nature of the ICF measurement framework and the different type of data this method collects in comparison to standard disability measurement (function and impact on day-to-day life) (WHO, 2001), the research team were unable to further categorise disability type.

The spread of disability types seen does not reflect the breakdown of disability types who reside in Scotland (Scottish Census, 2011) as the most prevalent disability type is hearing impairment.

Despite as many accessibility factors being accounted for as possible, this disparity may be due to people with non-physical disabilities experiencing challenges in relation to completing the questionnaire due to the nature of certain disabilities and the questionnaire format.

Sex – questionnaire

In terms of completion there is a relatively equal breakdown of males (51.8%) and females (47.1%), with a small proportion preferring not to say (1.2%). In terms of sex and participation in general, we would expect to see a significantly higher engagement rate for males in comparison to females (Rowe, 2019) highlighting differences in terms of the male/female participation in this study compared to male/female participation in sport in general.

Focus group demographics

Participant name	Gender	Age	Disability Type	Level of participation	Sport
Louise	F	26	Physical	National	Swimming
Gordon	M	15	Physical	National	Multi
Chris	M	25	Physical	Recreational	Wheelchair Sports
Conor	M		Physical	Recreational	Multi
Ross	M	22	Intellectual	National	Multi Sports
Alex	F	19	Physical	Recreational	Athletics
Conrad	M	13	Physical	National (junior level)	Wheelchair Sports
Juliet	F	41	Physical	Recreational	Yoga
Sarah	F	36	Physical	Recreational	Park run and fitness
Gill	F	42	Physical	Recreational	Boxing
Richard	M	69	Sensory	International	Bowls
Jessica	F		Physical/Sensory	Recreational	Athletics
David	M	42	Sensory	Recreational	Multi
George	M	33	Physical	Ex international	Athletics and boccia
Karen	F	20	Physical	Recreational	Powerchair Football
Joseph	M	50	Multi	International	Sailing, rugby, archery, bowls
Ellie	F	52	Multi	Recreational	Multi

Table 2: outlines the demographics of participants who engaged in the focus groups (pseudonyms are given to protect the identity of participants)

Within this study participants with a range of disability type, sex, experience level, sport and age engaged with the focus groups including n=7 females and n=9 males. Individual's experience level ranged from recreational (N=8) to international (n=3). The most common disability type of those taking part in the focus groups was physical disability (as per the breakdown of the questionnaire sample).

Participant motivations from a numerical perspective

Participant motivations for taking part in sport and physical activity

Participant motivations significantly influence engagement in sport (Ryan and Deci, 2017), therefore, it is important to gain an understanding of these factors and their influence on individuals' motivation to take part in sport.

Figure 3: Participant motivations for taking part in sport

Of the 450 responses 243 suggested that improving physical health was the most important motivator for physical activity. This data reflects research from Stephens et al., (2012) which highlights that individuals with a spinal cord injury are motivated to participate in sport due to the physical health improvements they experience as a result of participation.

These findings may suggest that PWD are motivated by improvements in physical health, this could be related to participants gaining feelings of competence as their physical ability improves (Deci and Ryan 2002; Ryan and Deci, 2017) and negative internal perceptions around capability are challenged (Patterson et al., 2012). Furthermore, similarly to findings by Ferri- Caruana et al., (2020) and Richardson et al., (2018) it could be argued that individuals feel that improved physical health through physical activity increases their autonomy and independence which then improves their quality of life and contributes to physiological needs such as feelings of autonomy and competency being met, which has previously been shown to positively influence continued participation in sport (Deci and Ryan, 2002).

In addition to physical health, mental health (MH) was also a significant motivator for individuals with disabilities who take part in sport in Scotland. This highlights three key findings; firstly, that PWD in Scotland are impacted by mental health, which corresponds with statistics from the Scottish Government (2017) that suggests PWD in Scotland have poorer mental wellbeing than non-disabled people. Secondly, that individuals with disabilities are consciously looking to improve their wellbeing, and thirdly, that participation in sport influences individuals 'mental health which suggests the need for more resources and time to be invested into creating more positive sporting opportunities as this will help to improve people with disabilities' mental health and increase motivation which will support participants to continue engaging in sport.

As this is the first study to research people with disabilities' participation motivations within Scotland there is no previous data to compare at this level (Davison and McPherson, 2021). However, this finding is similar to research by Conchar et al., (2016) and McKenzie et al., (2022) which suggests that improved mental health was one of the biggest motivators for engagement in sport for individuals with cerebral palsy across the world.

Figure 4: Participant Age and Fun as a motivator for sports participation

Within this study the second biggest motivator for participation in sport was fun, which has been cited as a key motive for sports participation for both PWD and non-disabled people (Kampe et al., 2014). Furthermore, this finding reflects research from McLoughlin et al., 2017, that suggests fun and enjoyment is a key motivator for PWD continued participation in sport. From a theoretical perspective, it could be argued that fun is a significant motivation due to correlation between enjoyment and high levels of intrinsic motivation (Ntoumis, 2005) which has been shown to influence continued participation (Deci, 2000).

In relation to age range, data highlights that taking part in sport for fun is a much more significant motivator for those aged between 12 and 24 compared to other age groups. These results reflect findings from Shields and Synott (2016), and Activity Alliance (2020) which found that young PWD engage in sport and physical activity to have fun and spend time with their peers.

This data around fun as a motivator and how this corresponds with age, provides insights which can be used to inform how organisations engage and motivate different age groups in Scotland, with particular emphasis being put on the psychological needs outlined in SDT (Deci and Ryan, 2002; Ryan and Deci, 2017). For example, this finding suggests that when engaging with young people a key focus must be on fun and enjoyment to increase intrinsic motivation, whereas focusing on the social connections (relatedness), wellbeing and physical health (physical competence) is more important when trying to increase intrinsic motivation and therefore engage with older people.

In addition to age, it is also important to consider the influence of disability type on specific motivations, therefore the figure below outlines the percentage of participants who selected fun as a motivator for sports participation and their disability type.

Figure 5: Percentage of participants who selected fun as a motivator for sports participation and disability type

Over 50% of participants from each disability category stated that fun and enjoyment is a significant motivator for engaging in sport and sport in physical activity. This reflects findings from previous research which highlights that people with sensory, physical and learning disabilities all participate in sport for fun and enjoyment (McLoughlin et al., 2017; Jaarsmaa et al., 2014 ; Hansen et al., 2021; Darcy and Dowse, 2013) which as previously has been shown to have a significant influence on intrinsic motivation (Ntoumis, 2005) which is essential for continued participation (Deci, 2000). In addition, fun was the most significant motivation for people with intellectual disabilities (ID), which suggests this group’s motivation is significantly enhanced by intrinsic factors. As there is limited literature comparing disability types and motivations it is difficult to make a direct comparison. However other scholars have found that fun and enjoyment is an important factor in sport and physical activity engagement for those with intellectual disabilities (Darcy and Dowse, 2013; Hansen et al., 2021).

Improved Mental Health as a Motivator for Participation

Participation in sport has been associated with improved mental health and overall wellbeing (Kapsal et al., 2019; Diaz et al., 2019). This is significant as PWD tend to have poorer mental health and overall wellbeing in comparison to non-disabled people (Scottish Government, 2017). Within

this study participants suggested that improved mental health is a key motivator for taking part in physical activity and sport (see figure three). Given the prevalence and importance of this factor within the current research and literature around participation, sport, disability and wellbeing (Kapsal et al., 2019; Diaz et al., 2019; Lumsdaine and Lord, 2021) the following figures explore the significance of improved mental health as a motivator for engagement in sport and physical activity in relation to age and disability type.

Figure 6: Age range and selection of improved mental health as a key motivation for sports participation

When examining mental health, age and motivation, it is apparent that as individuals get older, the positive impact that sport has on mental health becomes a more significant motivator for participation in sport until around the age of 49. The importance of this factor seems to decrease again after that age. This could be due to physical health becoming a more prominent factor as people become older (see figure 9).

Figure 7: Percentage of participants who selected improving mental health as a motivator for sports participation and disability type

Mental Health is an important factor for all disability types but for people with sensory disabilities it could be argued that this is even more significant. This could be due to the increased isolation and poorer mental wellbeing that this group experiences in comparison to other disability types (Office for National Statistics, 2022). Therefore, it could be argued that improved mental health is more of a priority for this group.

Given the quantitative nature of this data it is difficult to make an informed correlation with self-determination theory, however the focus groups conducted enabled deeper analysis and connections to be made, these are outlined later on in the study.

Improved physical health as a motivator for participation

Enhanced physical health is a well known benefit associated with engagement in sport and physical activity both for non disabled people (Khan et al., 2012) and PWD (Stephens et al., 2012; Darcy and Dowse, 2013). Furthermore, data from this research states that improved physical health is the most significant motivator for participation in sport for those with a disability in Scotland. In order to gain a greater understanding of this factor the figures below highlight data on improved physical health as a motivator and demographics such as disability type and age.

Figure 8: Percentage of participants who selected improved physical health as a motivator for sports participation and disability type

It is apparent that improved physical health as a result of participating in physical activity and/or sport is a significant motivator for all disability groups. In particular, those with sensory disabilities such as visual (67%) and hearing impairments (81%), therefore, it could be argued that people from these communities are more motivated by experiencing increasing levels of physical competency compared to those with intellectual disabilities who are more motivated by connections and enjoyment, these differences may be caused by the additional challenges deaf people experience when trying to communicate and connect with others during physical activity (Palmer, 2018) which may in fact decrease motivation, therefore it may be more common for deaf people to focus on developing and experiencing physical competence.

Figure 9: Age range and improve physical health as a motivator for sports participation

Similarly, to disability type, improving physical health is an important motivator for all age groups involved in this study. In comparison to other motivations, physical health has the least discrepancy between age groups. This could be due to all age groups understanding the physical benefits of sports participation and experiencing increased motivation as a result of increased feelings of physical competency (Ryan and Deci, 2017;2002).

Increased Confidence as a motivator for participation

Confidence is an important determinant of both psychological wellbeing (Stochl et al., 2019) and exercise adherence (Deci and Ryan, 2002). Therefore, it could be argued that developing confidence should be a priority in order to improve PWD poor wellbeing (Scottish Government, 2017) and low participation rates (Scottish Health Survey, 2020). It has been established that confidence can be increased through engagement in sport and physical activity (Labbé et al., 2019). The figures below examine whether and to what extent participants of different ages and disabilities are motivated to take part in sport due to the impact it can have on confidence levels (Marin-Urquiza, 2018).

Figure 10: Age range and Improved Confidence as a motivator for participation

Improved confidence is the most significant motivator for both the 16-24 age group and the 56-64 category followed by the 25-32 category. Confidence was the least important motivator for those in their 40's and 60's.

This finding could be explained by data that suggests young people tend to have lower self-confidence than adults (Burns et al., 2016), furthermore, it is well established that children and young PWD have lower levels of confidence, self-esteem and self-concept (Jaarsma et al., 2015) in comparison to non-disabled young people (Honey, et al., 2011; Karikuri et al., 2011). Therefore, it could be argued that the young people within this study are more focused on increasing their confidence and self-esteem through sport and have a greater need to feel competent in more general terms, in comparison to older participants who have higher confidence levels. However, it is apparent that between the ages of 49 and 65 increasing confidence becomes of greater importance again, studies suggest that self-esteem and confidence begin to decrease again around the age of 60 (Orth et al., 2010). These results highlight that for individuals with a disability self-esteem may begin to deteriorate earlier than non-disabled people, this may be due to the social, physical and emotional challenges that this community faces (Jaarsma et al., 2014; McLoughlin et al., 2017; Martin, 2013) therefore interventions which increase feelings of competency need to be implemented earlier than the non-disabled population to enable continued participation in sport (Ryan and Deci, 2017) and overall positive wellbeing (Stochl et al., 2019).

Figure 11: Percentage of participants who selected improving confidence as a motivator for sports participation and disability type

PWD tend to have low confidence levels, (Mustaq and Akhouri, 2016). However, within the quantitative section of this research increased confidence was a less significant motivation for participants in comparison to mental health, physical health and fun which highlights that although improving confidence can be a motivation for PWD it is not as important as other factors. This is a contradictory finding as feelings of competence and confidence are directly related to continued engagement in sport based on self-determination theory (Deci and Ryan, 2002; Ryan and Deci, 2017). However, it is apparent that other factors may be more influential in relation to sports participation.

Exploring people with disabilities' motivations for participation

In addition to quantitative data on individuals' motivations, focus groups were also utilised to delve deeper into people with disabilities' thoughts and experiences. Braun and Clark's (2006) six step framework was used to thematically analyse the data and this identified three key themes; the physical and mental impact of sports participation as a motivator, connections within sport and psychological disability factors. These themes and the subsequent sub themes will be discussed in depth below.

Theme 1: “Sport is good for my health” – the physical and mental impact of sports participation

Findings within the focus groups suggest that PWD in Scotland experience a range of physical and psychological benefits as a result of taking part in sport and physical activity.

Sub Theme: The psychological impact

Participants emphasised that taking part in sport “*gives you that buzz, it gives you that drive to go forward and do something. Not just a physical aspect, but also the psychological aspect is very, very important*”. **Richard, Bowler.**

This “buzz” may be connected to internal motivations such as achieving goals or experiencing enjoyment. Both these internal factors have been shown to directly influence individuals’ motivation and continued participation (Ryan and Deci, 2017), based upon the increase in internal motivation, which is enhanced by taking part in sport it could also be argued that sport and PA engagement acts as a facilitator for individuals with disabilities to achieve their goals and see progression. This is significant for PWD as within many areas of daily life such as employment opportunities for PWD to progress are limited due to a range of barriers including societal perceptions of disability (Moloney et al., 2019).

Based upon Self-Determination Theory (Ryan and Deci, 2017; Deci and Ryan, 2002) and participants’ experiences explored in the focus groups, it could be argued that practitioners and those working within the disability sport field should focus on increasing internal motivation by ensuring that fun and enjoyment is prioritised throughout sessions and that the activity being delivered is appropriate and meaningful which will allow participants to experience success and achieve their goals. This will then help to increase individuals’ motivation and continued engagement, as participation in activities can be dependent on whether the individuals feel like it is possible to achieve success (Bailey et al., 2013) as a result of correlations between confidence, competence and motivation which are key factors in relation to exercise adherence (Deci and Ryan, 2002).

In addition, exploring how success is defined may also be important as based on findings within this research it is apparent that individuals may define success in different ways to the non-disabled community, for example, by completing a successful transfer from a day chair to a sports chair or having the confidence to chat with others.

These factors and considerations combined are likely to increase internal motivation which will increase the likelihood of continued engagement in sport and physical activity (Ryan and Deci, 2017). This is significant discovery as it adds to our knowledge around how to increase low participation

rates (Scottish Health Survey, 2020) and improve PWD poor psychological wellbeing (Scottish Government, 2017) through sport.

In addition to providing individuals with a focus and an opportunity to relax and have fun, participants also expressed the significant impact that sport and physical activity has had on their self-confidence and self-esteem which tends to be lower in PWD (Jung et al., 2022; Salehi et al. 2014).

“So mental health wise, it just boosts me, it boosts my confidence and everything really.” **Gill, Boxer**

This finding mirrors the discoveries made within Lumsdaine and Lord’s (2021)’s autoethnographic research piece which suggests that participating in sport significantly improved individuals’ mental health, increased confidence and developed greater levels of self-esteem. From a theoretical perspective, this discovery suggests that participation in sport develops feelings of confidence and competence which then enhances motivation and promotes continued engagement (Ryan and Deci, 2017).

Subtheme: The physical impact of participation

Physical improvement was also a significant motivator for taking part in sport. Participants expressed that being active increased their functional ability.

“But But like, my body functions so much better than it could or even that like physiotherapy, physiotherapist expected to with the condition I have.” **Juliet, yoga participant and instructor**

This physical improvement positively impacted upon people’s quality of life, which can often be lower in PWD (Rajati et al., 2018). It could be argued that improved quality of life is a consequence of a variety of different psychological needs and factors interacting. Firstly, individuals experience physical progress and see what their bodies are capable of, which challenges internal ableism and the common narrative around disability which focuses on what individuals cannot achieve (Haegele et al., 2018) this results in participants increasing their self-concept and competence levels which develops greater levels of motivation (Ryan and Deci, 2017) as individuals feel more confident in their ability to successfully take part in sport and feel satisfied with their ability. This increase in confidence therefore results in continued participation in sport and physical activity (Ryan and Deci, 2017). This is an important finding as this explains the motivational process individuals may go through in relation to their physical function. Furthermore, it confirms that Deci and Ryan (2002) Self-Determination Theory can be used to understand PWD physical activity engagement in Scotland.

In addition to gaining a feeling of competence as a result of engaging in sport and experiencing physical improvement, PWD in this study also gained autonomy while engaging in sport by choosing to move in certain ways. Individuals noted that participating in sport was *“like a sense of freedom an opportunity to have fun and enjoy myself.”* **George, Boccia Player**

This is an important finding as participant motivation is directly linked to levels of autonomy (Ryan and Deci, 2017), however, many PWD have limited autonomy within day-to-day life (Adhikary et al., 2020; World Health Organisation, 2015) due to a variety of physical, individual, structural and societal factors (Van De Ven et al., 2008). Despite this though, findings within this study suggest that individuals who are involved in a positive sporting environment feel more autonomous due to having a greater sense of control over their bodies which results in participants being more motivated to take part in sport. This link between autonomy, engagement, PWD and sport has been established previously in literature around elite athletes who participate in equestrian events (Dashper, 2010). However, this is a new insight in relation to Scotland (Davison and McPherson, 2021) and adds new knowledge which suggests that feelings of increased autonomy are experienced by both recreational and elite athletes with a range of physical, sensory and learning disabilities. Furthermore, this suggests that if sport and physical activity is delivered in an inclusive and collaborative way it can be used as a tool to increase autonomy, which has been shown to be beneficial for people with disabilities’ quality of life and overall wellbeing (Mocha-Bonilla et al., 2018).

The findings within this theme highlight the correlation between the psychological and physical benefits of participation and individuals’ motivation to take part in sport which is a new finding within Scotland. This emphasizes the significance of initial engagement in sport for PWD in Scotland, as this allows participants to experience the benefits outlined above and enables their psychological needs to be met. This in turn may enhance motivation to continue participating (Ryan and Deci, 2017) which will positively impact participation rates (Scottish Health Survey, 2020) and improve PWD quality of life.

Theme 2: It’s All About the Connections

In contrast to the results of the questionnaire, which suggests that being part of a team and meeting new people was not one of the biggest motivators for PWD taking part in sport (see figure 5), findings within the focus groups illustrate that various types of connections significantly impact upon individuals’ motivation to participate in sport and physical activity.

Subtheme: Sports Staff and Coaches

Participants with physical, sensory and intellectual disabilities highlighted that coaches and staff significantly influence their experience and motivation when engaging physical activity and sport. This is a new finding within Scotland, however it is in agreement with previous studies by Ginis et al., (2021), Bentzen and Malmquist, (2022) and Banack et al., (2011). For example, specific factors such as a coach's attitude and approach towards an individual and their disability can either positively or negatively impact PWD motivation to participate in sport and physical activity (Darcy and Dowse 2013; Fitzgerald, 2018; Ginis et al., 2021; Shields and Synott, 2016). One participant noted that *"If someone knows about disability and is confident in knowing what to do then that makes the experience better"* **George, Boccia.**

Another suggested that one coach had altered their motivation for engaging in sport.

"I found that originally, I became active to try to lose weight. But my coach, you know, she's got so much drive, and she's motivating us so much. And she's putting so much into it, that the moment that actually it was, you know, like I caught it, you know, I caught the boxing bug, you know, and I've never watched boxing."
Gill, boxer.

From a Self Determination Theory perspective (Deci and Ryan, 2002; Ryan and Deci, 2017), this finding can be understood by focusing on whether the three psychological needs (autonomy, competence and relatedness) have been met. For example, if participants are involved in the session planning and decision-making process, they tend to feel more autonomous.

"Yeah, I think all my coaches have been helpful. I know one of my former coaches who sadly isn't with us anymore was really helpful he used to chat to me about what we are doing." **George, Boccia player**

Participants also suggested that if they are consulted about session adaptations for their specific needs, they are more engaged and are more likely to have a positive experience in sport and physical activity.

" if I was having a bad pain day, he'd ask me about how to adapt and what is best for me which was really good". **George, boccia player**

This could be related to participants experiencing greater feelings of autonomy and relatedness (Ryan and Deci, 2017) as by having open discussions around their needs, and coaches showing a willingness to adapt, individuals feel respected, valued and included (Bentzen and Malmquist, 2021).

This is an important discovery as it highlights the need for coaches to be collaborative and open to discussing disability which in the past has been avoided due to anxiety and a lack of knowledge

(Wareham et al., 2017; Lepage et al., 2020). Within this study and current research (Banack *et al.*, 2011), given the impact of a coach's attitude and approach to disability on participants' experiences and motivations, it is clear that support needs to be given to all coaches and sports staff in Scotland as this will enable coaches to feel comfortable and confident around disability which will create greater feelings of connectedness and autonomy between participants and staff which enhances motivation (Deci and Ryan, 2002).

Subtheme: Community

The sense of community between participants with disabilities was consistently mentioned throughout this research.

“And then the other one particular for me around kind of MS in the community is that the park run group for people with MS is the most supportive MS support group I'm in and the people there aren't there for Ms. They are there for like runninghaving that kind of really mixed community but just having a totally different understanding of why we run and also the support, kind of like come comes with that. That's been a really, really big part for me, and I didn't quite think this group would have been so important for the MS aspect, I thought, you know, I joined for kind of the running but actually, it turns out that like a lot of the kind of MS gets covered there as well.” Sarah, runner

“Within disability sport, in general, like all the people I know, the coaches like, I can't imagine not having that sort of network. I think it's given me the confidence to meet those friends.” Louise, Swimmer

Within disability sport in Scotland the supportive network between people with similar disabilities significantly contributed to individuals' experiences and motivation to engage in sport. Participants noted that being around other people with similar challenges made them feel part of something bigger than just a sports team or club.

“it's a family that's what the club is to most of us” Gordon, Multisport

Furthermore, a number of participants stated that being involved in sport and connecting with other PWD helped individuals to deal with the many challenges associated with having a disability.

“And it's going somewhere I feel accepted a bit more than like, and just general, everyday sort of life.” Louise, Swimmer

This suggests that participating in sport and being around others with disabilities increases feelings of relatedness and provides individuals with a greater sense of belonging which has been shown to

result in long term engagement in physical activity and sport (Ryan and Deci, 2017). These findings are similar to previous research by Goodwin et al., (2009), Goodwin et al., (2011), Bates et al., (2019), Allan et al., (2018) and Haslett et al., (2017) which found that individuals with a disability had an increased sense of belonging and ability to deal with specific challenges related to their disability as a result of being around others with similar disabilities. However, in addition to previous findings around finding a sense of belonging, relatedness and disability, this research adds a number of new insights, specifically around age and experience level. The focus groups highlighted that a diverse range of people including participants of different ages, participation levels and disability types developed a greater sense of belonging as a result of engaging in sport and physical activity. This is a new finding as this comparison between relatedness, physical activity, different ages, participation levels and disability types has not been made, particularly within Scotland.

In addition, analysis has also illustrated that interactions and connections within the disability sport community has increased both individuals sporting knowledge and feelings of competence, as well as coping strategies to manage living with a disability.

*“And I learned a lot from the different aspects of that, it's a very close-knit community as well. So it's been very good for that respect”. **Richard, Bowler***

This finding highlights a potential connection between the disabled community, learning, feelings of competency, coping skills and self-efficacy. It could be argued that as a consequence of interacting with other PWD and learning about their lived experience, individuals feel more competent about both their sporting capabilities and ability to tackle day to day challenges such as transferring from a day chair to a sports wheelchair. This suggests a correlation between relatedness and competence which is enhanced by interactions within the disability sport environment. This discovery is similar to findings by Stephens et al., (2012) who found that individuals felt more competent completing daily tasks as a result of connecting with others with disabilities. Furthermore, this suggests a potential link between interactions within the disabled community, motivation and coping strategies which needs to be further explored.

Theme 3: psychological factors associated with disability

Factors associated with the psychological impact of disability were also associated with participants' motivations and experiences.

Sub theme: “I think it's also helped me be more accepting of my body and its limitations” - feelings of acceptance.

Participants, particularly those with physical disabilities frequently mentioned that engaging in sport and physical activity has helped them to come to terms with their disability which echoes research by Smith et al., (2015), Ballas et al., (2020) and Lumsdaine and Lord (2021).

“It made me actually not hate the fact that I had a disability up until I actually started doing disability sport. I never, ever once said the word disability, disability or disabled, I refuse to, I wouldn't say that I had a disability. I wouldn't call myself a disabled person. Like, I just skirted around the entire topic, even though I was feeling about in my little racing chair as well. I was like, no, no, not at all. But it made me actually like, quite like proud of being part of something that was bigger than myself.” Alex, wheelchair racer

These findings suggest that taking part in sport and physical activity enables individuals to change their negative perceptions of disability, which are often caused by societal attitudes towards disability (Fitzgerald, 2018) and internal ableism (Brittain and Beacom, 2016), to a positive narrative which is built upon feelings of empowerment, connectedness and increased self-worth and self-esteem, which all link with key concepts from self-determination theory and continued exercise adherence (Deci and Ryan 2002). Therefore, it could be argued that increased self-acceptance is a key motivator for PWD participating in sport and physical activity in Scotland. This highlights the direct impact that connecting individuals with disabilities can have on both self-acceptance, self-worth (Reel and Bucciare, 2010) and engagement in sport.

Sub Theme: Changing the Focus

PWD often experience significant focus being put on their disability and limitations (Haegle et al., 2018), this stems from deeply ingrained concepts associated with the medical model of disability which suggests disability is abnormal (Smith and Bundon, 2018) and needs to be fixed (Goering, 2015). Within this study participants noted that taking in part in sport helped them to temporarily “forget” about their disability and the constant inequalities and difficulties they are faced with.

“And the Advantage of it is that I forget that I'm disabled.” Gill, Boxer.

This finding illustrates that sports participation enables individuals to focus on something other than their disability and the challenges associated with it, which is similar to research by Stephens et al., (2012) who found that a key benefit of participating in sport for people with a spinal cord injury was the element of escapism that sport brings. Furthermore, this discovery suggests that many people use sport and physical activity participation as a coping mechanism to deal with the significant psychological impact that is associated with having a disability (Namkung and Carr, 2020) which is a new finding, particularly within Scotland.

Overview

Overall, this study looked to explore the participation and motivation of PWD living in Scotland. Findings within this thesis indicate that participants have several motivations for taking part in sport and physical activity such as the benefits of participation, which include improved physical health, increased confidence and greater levels of autonomy, the connections made within the disability sport community and psychological factors associated with disability. Furthermore, the motivations for participation outlined within this thesis directly relate to the psychological needs associated with self-determination theory (Deci and Ryan, 2002) which highlights that this theory can be used to understand people with disabilities' sport and physical activity engagement in Scotland. For example, the social aspect of taking part in sport and the connection between participants within the disabled community increases relatedness as participants feel a sense of belonging due to spending time with other people with disabilities. Moreover, individuals develop feelings of competency around how to deal with challenges, both within a sporting context and day to day life as a result of speaking to others who are in a similar situation which increases the likelihood of continued engagement (Ryan and Deci, 2017) and improved quality of life.

In addition, it is apparent that engagement in sport can be used as a coping mechanism for dealing with the social, physical and environmental challenges that are associated with having a disability (Fitzgerald, 2018; Amad, 2012), as it provides a sense of escapism (Stephens et al., 2012) and supports participants to change their perceptions and internal narrative around disability which can often be negative as a result of internalised ableism (Brittain and Beacom, 2016).

The relationship between self-determination theory (Ryan and Deci, 2017; Deci and Ryan, 2002) and sports participation has been explored within different age groups, experience levels and disability types which is a new observation as previous literature tends to examine elite athletes (McLoughlin et al., 2017; Ballas et al., 2020) or those in rehab with an acquired disability (Michalovic et al., 2019). Therefore, this thesis brings new insights which add to our knowledge of this topic, specifically around people with disabilities' sports participation and motivations in Scotland (Davison and McPherson, 2021). Finally, unlike many studies within the field of disability sport and research this study utilises individuals lived experience to provide a greater understanding of the motivations PWD experience within Scotland (Quinn et al., 2020).

Recommendations for Practitioners

Based upon the findings within this study, recommendations for sports practitioners and stakeholders on increasing PWD motivation levels are threefold. Firstly, given the influence that a

coach's attitude and approach towards disability can have on individuals' motivation for participation in sport and physical activity and overall experience, it would be beneficial for all staff and coaches involved in delivering sport to undertake disability awareness training as this will enable practitioners to be confident in talking about disability and creating adaptations which has been shown within this study to enhance motivation levels by increasing autonomy and relatedness (Deci and Ryan, 2002; Ryan and Deci, 2017). Secondly, sport and physical activity sessions must focus on creating fun, enjoyable and meaningful participation opportunities that enable individuals to experience success as this will create greater levels of internal motivation and support continued engagement (Bailey et al., 2013), particularly for young PWD (Activity Alliance 2020; Shields and Synott, 2016). Finally, it is apparent that people with different disabilities have similar motivations for participating in sport and physical activity, however where this differs is in the significance of each factor and how these are met for different disability groups. For example, improving mental health and confidence is a significant motivator for people with sensory disabilities, whereas people with intellectual disabilities are more focused on enjoyment and making connections with other people with disabilities. These findings suggest the need to create a more targeted and individualised approach when trying to engage with different target groups.

Limitations and Future Directions

Despite a range of new insights this research does have a number of limitations, for example, although all disability groups were represented within this study, people with sensory and intellectual disabilities made up a very small proportion of the sample both within the focus groups and questionnaire, which resulted in these groups thoughts and experiences being less represented throughout this paper. Although, this study compared the motivations of people with different disabilities, due to the size and scale of the project, analysis and comparison of motivations between those with congenital and acquired disability was not possible. However, given the prominence of this topic within the field a comparative study which explores those with congenital and acquired disabilities motivations could add rich insights into the academic research on this topic and have meaningful practical implications for the sector.

Furthermore, as the questionnaire and focus groups took place online, individuals who face digital poverty, particularly those who can't afford accessible technology were unable to engage with the project which again limits the sample size and representation within the project. Therefore, future research needs to employ a more targeted approach to ensure all disabilities groups can be represented. This could be achieved by implementing different data collection approaches which target specific disability groups as it has become apparent throughout the research process that

creating data collection tools e.g., questionnaires that are accessible for all impairment groups presents many challenges such as ensuring the content and language is appropriate and that the questionnaire format can be accessed by everyone including those who use screen readers. Furthermore, a combination of face to face and online data collection methods would enable a more diverse group of people to participate and potentially increase the number of responses and richness of data. In addition, one of the key findings which suggests that sports participation improves individual's improved coping skills and ability to deal with challenges associated with their disability needs to be further explored to examine the relationship between increased coping mechanisms and participation. This would allow individuals within the field to have a greater understanding of how participation and physical activity links with coping mechanisms, specifically investigating which areas and styles of coping are being developed and whether this differs depending on individuals' impairment type. Finally, this study has established a correlation between concepts within the self-determination theory (Deci and Ryan, 2002; Ryan and Deci, 2017) and sports participation for PWD in Scotland. This has been achieved by exploring people with disabilities' experiences and current theory. However, this connection has not been measured objectively, therefore, to further understanding of sports participation and SDT, it is recommended that future work in this field utilises a mixed methods approach to measure PWD levels of autonomy, competence and connectedness prior to taking part in sport and after a set period of time to create an objective indicator as to whether participating in sport increases these psychological needs.

Conclusion

The aim of this research was to gain insight into the motivations of individuals who currently participate in sport and physical activity in Scotland. It also sought to achieve four objectives which were to examine the correlation between engagement in sport for people with a disability in Scotland and self-determination theory (Deci and Ryan, 2002; Ryan and Deci, 2017). Secondly, to study the similarities and differences in motivations of people from different disability groups who participate in sport. Thirdly to provide suggestions for future research in this area based upon the findings of the study and finally, to advise individuals within the sports sector on ways to enhance the experiences and motivation levels of individuals taking part in sport who have a disability.

This study has addressed a number of gaps within the current literature surrounding disability, sports participation and motivations in Scotland. It explored the motivations of people with a variety

of different disabilities, such as those with sensory, physical and intellectual disabilities, as this has never been examined in Scotland before (Davison and McPherson, 2021). The findings provide new insights which suggest people with different disability types have similar motivations for participating in sport and physical activity, however where this differs is in the significance of each factor and how these are met for different disability groups.

Both the qualitative and quantitative results established that the physical and psychological impacts of sport participation significantly influenced individual's motivation around engagement and there was found to be connections between the psychological needs outlined in self-determination theory and participant motivations (Deci and Ryan, 2002; Ryan and Deci, 2017).

The study highlighted the importance of fun and enjoyment, especially for those of a younger age and those with an intellectual disability. It suggested the importance of mental health as a motivator especially for those with a hearing impairment and found that across disability groups the importance of mental health as a motivator diminished in older age groups. A pattern emerged in relation to the development of confidence through sport where older and younger participants found this to be of greater significance. It was also found that connections play a significant role in that staff and coaches can influence motivation levels, and relationships with others who have a disability can increase a sense of belonging and develop a positive self-concept. It also appeared that engagement in sport and physical activity facilitated an escape from the challenges associated with having a disability.

Results from this study suggest that confidence around discussing disability and participation needs to increase amongst those who work in this field potentially through awareness training.

Meaningful and enjoyable sessions should be created regardless of disability, however a targeted approach is needed when engaging with different disability groups to reflect their specific physiological and physical needs.

References

Abidi, J. and Sharma, D., 2014. Poverty, disability, and employment: Global perspectives from the National Centre for Promotion of Employment for Disabled People. *Career Development and Transition for Exceptional Individuals*, 37(1), pp.60-68.

Activity Alliance (2022b) *Inclusive recovery report: "Include me as we return to activity"*. Available at:

<https://www.activityalliance.org.uk/how-we-help/research/7589-inclusive-recovery-report-include-me-as-we-return-to-activity> (Accessed December 2022)

Activity Alliance (2020) *My Active Future: Including every child (March 2020)*. Available at: <https://www.activityalliance.org.uk/how-we-help/research/5658-my-active-future-including-every-child-march-2020> (Accessed November 2022)

Adhikary, D. et al. (2020). Sports and Social Capital: A Qualitative Study on Women Athletes with Disabilities. *discourse*, 8, p.9.

Aherne, C. and Coughlan, B., (2017). A preliminary investigation of the suitability of aquatics for people with severe and profound intellectual disabilities. *Journal of Intellectual Disabilities*, 21(2), pp.118-133.

Ahmad, W., (2012). Barriers of inclusive education for children with intellectual disability. *Indian Streams Research Journal*, 2(2), pp.1-4.

Allan, V. et al. (2018). Narratives of participation among individuals with physical disabilities: A life-course analysis of athletes' experiences and development in parasport. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 37, pp.170-178.

Allan, V. et al. (2020). From the athletes' perspective: A social-relational understanding of how coaches shape the disability sport experience. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, 32(6), pp.546-564.

Anastasiou, D. and Kauffman, J.M., (2012). Disability as cultural difference: Implications for special education. *Remedial and special education*, 33(3), pp.139-149.

Andersen, M.H. et al. (2019). The social and psychological health outcomes of team sport participation in adults: An integrative review of research. *Scandinavian journal of public health*, 47(8), pp.832-850

Applebay, K, and Foster E, (2013) in Roper, E. A. (2013) *Gender Relations in Sport*. 1st ed. 2013.

Atkinson, M., (2012). The empirical strikes back: Doing realist ethnography. In *Qualitative research on sport and physical culture*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited.

Bailey, R. et al. (2013). Why do children take part in, and remain involved in sport? A literature review and discussion of implications for sports coaches. *International Journal of Coaching Science*, 7(1).

Ballas, J. *et al.* (2020). Elite-level athletes with physical impairments: Barriers and facilitators to sport participation. *Disability & Society*, pp.1-20.

Barnes, J. *et al.* (2012). Standardized use of the terms "sedentary" and "sedentary behaviours". *Applied Physiology Nutrition and Metabolism-Physiologie Appliquee Nutrition Et Metabolisme*, 37, pp.540-542.

Banack, H.R. *et al.*, 2011. Coach autonomy support, basic need satisfaction, and intrinsic motivation of paralympic athletes. *Research quarterly for exercise and sport*, 82(4), pp.722-730.

Barnes, C., (2012). Re-thinking disability, work and welfare. *Sociology Compass*, 6(6), pp.472-484.

Bates, L. *et al.* (2019). 'A level playing field': Young people's experiences of wheelchair basketball as an enabling place. *Health & Place*, 60, p.102192.

Bath, B. *et al.* (2014). A biopsychosocial profile of adult Canadians with and without chronic back disorders: a population-based analysis of the 2009-2010 Canadian Community Health Surveys. *BioMed Research International*, 2014.

Bentzen, M. and Malmquist, L.K., (2022). Differences in participation across physical activity contexts between adolescents with and without disability over three years: a self-determination theory perspective. *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 44(9), pp.1660-1668.

Bezyak, J.L. *et al.* (2020). Community participation and public transportation barriers experienced by people with disabilities. *Disability and rehabilitation*, 42(23), pp.3275-3283.

Bloemen, M.A. *et al.* (2015). Factors associated with physical activity in children and adolescents with a physical disability: a systematic review. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*, 57(2), pp.137-148.

Bodde, A.E. and Seo, D.C., (2009). A review of social and environmental barriers to physical activity for adults with intellectual disabilities. *Disability and health journal*, 2(2), pp.57-66.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3: 77– 101.

Braun, V. *et al.* (2016). Using thematic analysis in sport and exercise research. In *Routledge handbook of qualitative research in sport and exercise* (pp. 213-227). Routledge.

Brighton, J. *et al.* (2021). Moving Beyond Models: Theorizing Physical Disability in the Sociology of Sport. *Sociology of Sport Journal*, 38(4), pp.386-398.

- Brighton, J. et al. (2021). Moving Beyond Models: Theorizing Physical Disability in the Sociology of Sport. *Sociology of Sport Journal*, 38(4), pp.386-398.
- Brittain, I. and Beacom, A., (2016). Leveraging the London 2012 Paralympic Games: What legacy for disabled people?. *Journal of sport and social issues*, 40(6), pp.499-521.
- Brittain, I. et al. (2020). Ableism as a regulator of social practice and disabled peoples' self-determination to participate in sport and physical activity. *Leisure Studies*, 39(2), pp.209-224.
- Burchardt, T. et al. (2015). Public policy and inequalities of choice and autonomy. *Social Policy & Administration*, 49(1), pp.44-67.
- Burns, K.M. et al. (2016). Confidence—More a personality or ability trait? It depends on how it is measured: A comparison of young and older adults. *Frontiers in psychology*, 7, p.518.
- Bush, A. et al. (2013). Disability [sport] and discourse: Stories within the Paralympic legacy. *Reflective Practice*, 14(5), pp.632-647.
- Caton, S. et al. (2012). Healthy lifestyles for adults with intellectual disability: knowledge, barriers, and facilitators. *Journal of Intellectual and Developmental Disability*, 37(3), pp.248-259.
- Coe, R.J., (2012). Conducting your research. *Research methods and methodologies in education*, pp.41-52.
- Cottingham, M. et al. (2018). Women of power soccer: exploring disability and gender in the first competitive team sport for powerchair users. *Sport in Society*, 21(11), pp.1817-1830
- Darcy, S. and Dowse, L., (2013). In search of a level playing field—the constraints and benefits of sport participation for people with intellectual disability. *Disability & Society*, 28(3), pp.393-407..
- Dashper, K., (2010). 'It's a Form of Freedom': The experiences of PWD within equestrian sport. *Annals of Leisure Research*, 13(1-2), pp.86-101.
- Davison, R. C. R., and McPherson, G. (2021). Disability Sport Research Review. Observatory for Sport in Scotland. Available at: <https://oss.scot/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/Disability-Sport-Review-Aug-2021-final.pdf>
- Davison R. C. R. et al. (in review). *Understanding Disability and Sport in Scotland*.
- Deans, S. et al. (2012). Motivations and barriers to prosthesis users participation in physical activity, exercise and sport: a review of the literature. *Prosthetics and orthotics international*, 36(3), pp.260-269.

Deci, E.L. and Ryan, R.M., (2000). The " what" and " why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological inquiry*, 11(4), pp.227-268.

Deci, E.L. and Ryan, R.M., (2002). *Self-determination research: Reflections and future directions*

Degener, T., (2017). A new human rights model of disability. In *The United Nations convention on the rights of persons with disabilities* (pp. 41-59). Springer, Cham.

Diaz, R. et al. (2019). Impact of adaptive sports participation on quality of life. *Sports medicine and arthroscopy review*, 27(2), pp.73-82.

Dyson, S. and Berghs, M., (2019). Ethnicity, disability and chronic illness. In *Understanding 'race' and ethnicity* (pp. 181-200). Policy Press.

Easterlin, M.C. et al. (2019). Association of team sports participation with long-term mental health outcomes among individuals exposed to adverse childhood experiences. *JAMA pediatrics*, 173(7), pp.681-688.

Esposito, P.E. et al. (2012). Physical activity patterns of youth with Down syndrome. *Intellectual and developmental disabilities*, 50(2), pp.109-119.

Fasczewski, K.S. et al. (2018). Physical activity motivation and benefits in people with multiple sclerosis. *Disability and rehabilitation*, 40(13), pp.1517-1523.

Feitosa, L.C. et al. (2017) The effect of adapted sports in quality of life and biopsychosocial profile of children and adolescents with cerebral palsy. *Revista Paulista de Pediatria*, 35, pp.429-435.#

Fitzgerald, H., (2018). Disability and barriers to inclusion. In *The Palgrave handbook of Paralympic studies* (pp. 55-70). Palgrave Macmillan, London.

Fitzgerald, H.,(2012). Paralympic athletes and "knowing disability". *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 59(3), pp.243-255.

Frederick, A. and Shifrer, D., (2019). Race and disability: From analogy to intersectionality. *Sociology of Race and Ethnicity*, 5(2), pp.200-214.

Gallagher, P. et al. (2011). Environmental barriers, activity limitations and participation restrictions experienced by people with major limb amputation. *Prosthetics and Orthotics International*, 35(3), pp.278-284.

Ginis, K.A.M., et al. (2021). Participation of people living with disabilities in physical activity: a global perspective. *The Lancet*, 398(10298), pp.443-455.

- Goering, S., (2015). Rethinking disability: the social model of disability and chronic disease. *Current reviews in musculoskeletal medicine*, 8(2), pp.134-138.
- Goodley, D. (2012). The Psychology of Disability. In *Routledge Handbook to Disability Studies*, ed. N. Watson, A. Roulstone, and C. Thomas, 310–323. London: Routledge
- Goodley, D. and Swartz, L., (2016). The place of disability. In *Disability in the global south* (pp. 69-83). Springer, Cham.
- Goodley, D., (2011). Social psychoanalytic disability studies. *Disability & Society*, 26(6), pp.715-728.
- Goodwin, D.L et al. (2009). It's okay to be a quad: Wheelchair rugby players' sense of community. *Adapted physical activity quarterly*, 26(2), pp.102-117.
- Goodwin, D.L. et al. (2011). Connecting through summer camp: Youth with visual impairments find a sense of community. *Adapted physical activity quarterly*, 28(1), pp.40-55.
- Graupensperger, S. et al. (2021). Prospective associations between sport participation and indices of mental health
- Haegele, J.A. and Hodge, S.,(2016). Disability discourse: Overview and critiques of the medical and social models. *Quest*, 68(2), pp.193-206.lth across adolescence. *Journal of youth and adolescence*, 50(7), pp.1450-1463.
- Haegele, J.A. et al. (2018). Females with visual impairments in physical education: Exploring the intersection between disability and gender identities. *Research quarterly for exercise and sport*, 89(3), pp.298-308.
- Hansen, E., et al. (2021). Adolescents with intellectual disability (ID) and their perceptions of, and motivation for, physical activity and organised sports. *Sport, Education and Society*, pp.1-14.
- Haslett, D. and Smith, B., (2020). Viewpoints toward disability: Conceptualizing disability in adapted physical education. In *Routledge handbook of adapted physical education* (pp. 48-64). Routledge.
- Haslett, D. et al. (2017). The psychological influences on participation in wheelchair rugby: a social relational model of disability. *Auc Kinanthropologica*, 53(1), pp.60-78.
- Heerkens, Y.F. et al. (2018). Reconsideration ICF scheme. *Disability Rehabilitation*, 40(1), pp.121-122.
- Heron, L. et al. (2019). Direct healthcare costs of sedentary behaviour in the UK. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*, 73(7), 625-629. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech-2018-211758>

- Honey, A. *et al.* (2011). The mental health of young people with disabilities: impact of social conditions. *Social psychiatry and psychiatric epidemiology*, 46(1), pp.1-10.
- Hums, M.A. (2016). "Women with disabilities in sport", in Staurowsky, E. (ed) *Women in Sport*. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.
- Ives, B. *et al.*(2021). 'I'll always find a perfectly justified reason for not doing it': Challenges for disability sport and physical activity in the United Kingdom. *Sport in Society*, 24(4), pp.588-606.
- Jaarsma, E.A. *et al.* (2014a). Barriers to and facilitators of sports participation in people with visual impairments. *Adapted Physical Activity Quarterly*, 31(3), pp.240-264.
- Jaarsma, E.A. *et al.* (2014b). Barriers to and facilitators of sports participation for people with physical disabilities: A systematic review. *Scandinavian journal of medicine & science in sports*, 24(6), pp.871-881.
- Jaarsma, E.A. *et al.* (2015). Barriers and facilitators of sports in children with physical disabilities: a mixed-method study. *Disability and rehabilitation*, 37(18), pp.1617-1625.
- Jaarsma, E.A. *et al.* (2016). Sports participation after rehabilitation: Barriers and facilitators. *Journal of rehabilitation medicine*, 48(1), pp.72-79.
- Jesus, T.S. *et al.* (2021). Lockdown-related disparities experienced by PWD during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic: Scoping review with thematic analysis. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(12), p.6178.
- Jung, Y.H. *et al.* (2022). Impact of the Acceptance of Disability on Self-Esteem among Adults with Disabilities: A Four-Year Follow-Up Study. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(7), p.3874.
- Kämpfe A. *et al.* (2014). MULTIPLICITY AND DEVELOPMENT OF ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION: A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN GERMAN ELITE ATHLETES WITH AND WITHOUT A DISABILITY. *European journal of adapted physical activity*, 7(1).
- Kapsal, N.J. *et al.* (2019). Effects of physical activity on the physical and psychosocial health of youth with intellectual disabilities: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 16(12), pp.1187-1195.
- Kariuki, M. *et al.* (2011). Mental health trajectories of young people after disability onset. *Disability and health journal*, 4(2), pp.91-101.

- Khan, K.M. *et al.* (2012). *Sport and exercise as contributors to the health of nations*. The Lancet, 380(9836), pp.59-64.
- King, S., (2016). In defence of realist tales. In *Routledge handbook of qualitative research in sport and exercise* (pp. 313-323). Routledge.
- Labbé, D., Miller, W.C. and Ng, R., 2019. Participating more, participating better: Health benefits of adaptive leisure for people with disabilities. *Disability and health journal*, 12(2), pp.287-295.
- Lam, J.R. *et al.* (2019). The association between socioeconomic status and psychological distress: a within and between twin study. *Twin Research and Human Genetics*, 22(5), pp.312-320.
- Lee, J.E. *et al.* (2018). The role of youth sports in promoting children's physical activity and preventing pediatric obesity: a systematic review. *Behavioral Medicine*, 44(1), pp.62-76.
- Lepage, P. *et al.* (2020). Development and acquisition of knowledge of youth parasport coaches. *Adapted Physical Activity Quarterly*, 37(1), pp.72-89.
- Lindsay, S. *et al.* (2018). A systematic review of the benefits of hiring people with disabilities. *Journal of occupational rehabilitation*, 28(4), pp.634-655.
- Lubin, A. and Feeley, C. (2016) 'Transportation Issues of Adults on the Autism Spectrum: Findings from Focus Group Discussions', *Transportation Research Record*, 2542(1), pp. 1–8. doi: .
- Lumsdaine, G. and Lord, R. (2021). (Re)Creating a healthy self in and through disability sport: Autoethnographic chaos and quest stories from a sportswoman with cerebral palsy. *Disability and Society*.
- Mallett, R. and Runswick-Cole, K., (2014). *Approaching disability: Critical issues and perspectives*. Routledge.
- Marin-Urquiza, A. *et al.* (2018). Athletic identity and self-esteem among active and retired Paralympic athletes. *European Journal of Sport Science*, 18(6), pp.861-871.
- Martin Ginis, K.A., *et al.* (2016). A systematic review of review articles addressing factors related to physical activity participation among children and adults with physical disabilities. *Health psychology review*, 10(4), pp.478-494.
- Martin, J.J., (2013). Benefits and barriers to physical activity for individuals with disabilities: a social-relational model of disability perspective. *Disability and rehabilitation*, 35(24), pp.2030-2037.

Mascarinas A., and Blauwet C. (2018) *Policy and Advocacy Initiatives to Promote the Benefits of Sports Participation for Individuals with Disability*. In: De Luigi A. (eds) *Adaptive Sports Medicine*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-56568-2_30

McCartney, G. *et al.* (2015). Explaining the excess mortality in Scotland compared with England: pooling of 18 cohort studies. *J Epidemiol Community Health*, 69(1), pp.20-27.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/jech-2014-206482>

McCarty, N. *et al.* (2022). Motivation for Physical Activity in Adults With Multiple Sclerosis: A Self-determination Theory-Based Approach. *International Journal of MS Care*, 24(3), pp.117-123.

McKenzie, G *et al.* (2022). 'Finding what works for me'—a qualitative study of factors influencing community gym participation for young adults with cerebral palsy. *Disability and Rehabilitation*, pp.1-8.

McLoughlin, G. *et al.* (2017). Sport participation for elite athletes with physical disabilities: Motivations, barriers, and facilitators. *Adapted Physical Activity Quarterly*, 34(4), pp.421-441.

McPherson, G. *et al.* (2016). Elite athletes or superstars? Media representation of para-athletes at the Glasgow 2014 Commonwealth Games. *Disability & society*, 31(5), pp.659-675.

Melzer, D. *et al.* (2015). *The Age UK almanac of disease profiles in later life A reference on the frequency of major diseases, conditions and syndromes affecting older people in England*. Retrieved from https://www.ageuk.org.uk/Documents/EN-GB/Forprofessionals/Research/Age_UK_almanac_FINAL_9Oct15.pdf?dtrk=true

Michalovic, E. *et al.* (2019). Motivation and participation in daily and social activities among adults with spinal cord injury: Applying self-determination theory. *Disability and health journal*, 12(3), pp.489-494.

Misener, L. *et al.* (2013). Beyond Olympic legacy: Understanding Paralympic legacy through a thematic analysis. *Journal of sport management*, 27(4), pp.329-341.

Mocha-Bonilla Julio, A. *et al.* (2018). Effects of motivation in sports: a study with people with visual impairment. *International Journal*, 74(1/2), pp.16-24.

Moloney, M.E., *et al* (2019). "Going the extra mile": disclosure, accommodation, and stigma management among working women with disabilities. *Deviant behavior*, 40(8), pp.942-956.

Mulligan, H.F. *et al.* (2012). Barriers to physical activity for people with long-term neurological conditions: a review study. *Adapted Physical Activity Quarterly*, 29(3), pp.243-265.

- Mushtaq, S. and Akhouri, D., (2016). Self esteem, anxiety, depression and stress among physically disabled people. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 3(4), pp.125-132.
- Namkung, E.H. and Carr, D., (2020). The psychological consequences of disability over the life course: Assessing the mediating role of perceived interpersonal discrimination. *Journal of health and social behavior*, 61(2), pp.190-207.
- National Health Service Wales. (2022). *Overweight and Obesity*. Available at: [https://phw.nhs.wales/topics/overweight-and-obesity/#:~:text=Around%2060%25%20of%20adults%20\(16,of%20those%20classified%20as%20obese](https://phw.nhs.wales/topics/overweight-and-obesity/#:~:text=Around%2060%25%20of%20adults%20(16,of%20those%20classified%20as%20obese) (Accessed December 2022)
- Newitt, R. *et al.* (2016). Understanding factors that influence participation in physical activity among people with a neuromusculoskeletal condition: a review of qualitative studies. *Disability and rehabilitation*, 38(1), pp.1-10.
- Nicholls, J.G., (1984). Achievement motivation: Conceptions of ability, subjective experience, task choice, and performance. *Psychological review*, 91(3), p.328.
- Nosek, M.A. *et al.* (2003). Self-esteem and women with disabilities. *Social science & medicine*, 56(8), pp.1737-1747.
- Oberle, E. *et al.* (2019). Benefits of extracurricular participation in early adolescence: Associations with peer belonging and mental health. *Journal of youth and adolescence*, 48(11), pp.2255-2270.
- Office for National Statistics (2022). *"Disability and Wellbeing"*. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/healthandsocialcare/disability/datasets/disabilityandwellbeing> (Accessed December 2022)
- Office For National Statistics. (2021). *Life expectancy for local areas of the UK: between 2001 to 2003 and 2018 to 2020* . Available at <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/healthandsocialcare/healthandlifeexpectancies/bulletins/lifeexpectancyforlocalareasoftheuk/between2001to2003and2018to2020> (accessed December 2022)
- Oliver, M., (2013). The social model of disability: Thirty years on. *Disability & society*, 28(7), pp.1024-1026.
- Oliver, M., (2017). Defining impairment and disability: Issues at stake. In *Disability and equality law* (pp. 3-18). Routledge.

- Orth, U. *et al.* (2010). Self-esteem development from young adulthood to old age: a cohort-sequential longitudinal study. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 98(4), p.645. Honey, A., Oviedo, G.R. *et al.* (2017). Sedentary and physical activity patterns in adults with intellectual disability. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 14(9), p.1027.
- Owens, J., (2015). Exploring the critiques of the social model of disability: the transformative possibility of Arendt's notion of power. *Sociology of health & illness*, 37(3), pp.385-403.
- Palmer, M. and Harley, D., (2012). Models and measurement in disability: an international review. *Health Policy and Planning*, 27(5), pp.357-364.
- Petasis, A., (2019). Discrepancies of the medical, social and biopsychosocial models of disability; A comprehensive theoretical framework. *The International Journal of Business Management and Technology*, 3(4), pp.42-54.
- Pitney, W.A. and Parker, J., (2009). *Qualitative research in physical activity and the health professions* (pp. 63-65). Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.
- Potrac, P. *et al.* (2014). Interpretivism. In *Research methods in sports coaching* (pp. 31-41). Routledge.
- Priestley, A., (2021). *Health inequality and COVID-19 in Scotland*. URL: [https://www.gov.scot/publications/the-impacts-of-Covid-19-on-equality-in-Scotland/\(accessed December 2022\)](https://www.gov.scot/publications/the-impacts-of-Covid-19-on-equality-in-Scotland/(accessed%20December%202022)).
- Quinn, N. *et al.* (2020). All for one and one for all? Integration in high-performance sport. *Managing sport and leisure*, pp.1-19.
- Rajati, F. *et al.* (2018). Quality of life predictors in physically disabled people. *Journal of education and health promotion*, 7.
- Ramulu, P.Y. *et al.* (2012). Real-world assessment of physical activity in glaucoma using an accelerometer. *Ophthalmology*, 119(6), pp.1159-1166.
- Reel, J. J., and Bucciare, R. A. (2010). Ableism and Body Image: Conceptualizing How Individuals Are Marginalized. *Women in Sport and Physical Activity Journal* 19, 1, 91-97, available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1123/wspaj.19.1.91>> (Accessed December 2022)
- Riddle, C.A., (2013). Defining disability: Metaphysical not political. *Medicine, health care and philo*

Rimmer, J.H. and Rowland, J.L., (2008). Health promotion for people with disabilities: Implications for empowering the person and promoting disability-friendly environments. *American Journal of Lifestyle Medicine*, 2(5), pp.409-420.

Rolfe, D.E. *et al.* (2012). Balancing safety and autonomy: Structural and social barriers affecting the exercise participation of women with disabilities in community recreation and fitness facilities. *Qualitative research in sport, exercise and health*, 4(2), pp.265-283.

Rowe, N.F., (2019). Sports participation in Scotland: trends and future prospects. *Observatory for Sport in Scotland: Kelso, UK.*

Ryan, R.M. and Deci, E.L., (2017). *Self-determination theory: Basic psychological needs in motivation, development, and wellness.* Guilford Publications.

Saebu, M. (2013). Motivation for physical activity in young adults with physical disabilities during a rehabilitation stay: a longitudinal test of self-determination theory. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 43(3), pp.612-625.

Salehi, M. *et al.* (2015). The relationship between self-esteem and sexual self-concept in people with physical-motor disabilities. *Iranian Red Crescent Medical Journal*, 17(1).

Scope. (2022) *Disability facts and figures.* Available at: <https://www.scope.org.uk/media/disability-facts-figures/> (accessed December 2022)

Scottish Census (2011). *Health.* Available at: <https://www.scotlandscensus.gov.uk/census-results/at-a-glance/health/> (Accessed December 2022)

Scottish Government (2022) *National Care Service - health and demographic profile: evidence.* Available at <https://www.gov.scot/publications/national-care-service-scotlands-health-demographic-profile/pages/4/> (Accessed December 2022)

Scottish Health Survey (2019). *Scottish Health Survey 2019 Volume 1 Main Report.* Available At: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-health-survey-2019-volume-1-main-report/pages/10/#:~:text=In%202019%2C%20all%20adults%20recorded,recorded%20for%20men%20and%20women.> (Accessed December 2022)

Scottish Health Survey (2020) Section five - Physical activity and sport. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-household-survey-2020-telephone-survey-key-findings/pages/6/#:~:text=64%25%20of%20adults%20with%20a,in%20the%20last%20four%20weeks.> (Accessed May 2022)

Scottish Health Survey (2022). *The Scottish Health Survey 2021 - volume 1: main report*. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-health-survey-2021-volume-1-main-report/> (accessed December 2022)

Shields, N. and Synnot, A., (2016). Perceived barriers and facilitators to participation in physical activity for children with disability: a qualitative study. *BMC paediatrics*, 16(1), pp.1-10.

Shields, N. *et al.* (2012). Perceived barriers and facilitators to physical activity for children with disability: a systematic review. *British journal of sports medicine*, 46(14), pp.989-997.

Smith, B. & Sparkes, AC (eds) 2016, *Routledge Handbook of Qualitative Research in Sport and Exercise*, Taylor & Francis Group, London. Available from: ProQuest Ebook Central.

Smith, B. and Bundon, A., (2018). Disability models: Explaining and understanding disability sport in different ways. In *The Palgrave handbook of paralympic studies* (pp. 15-34). Palgrave Macmillan, London.

Smith, B. and Sparkes, A.C., (2019). Disability, sport and physical activity. In *Routledge handbook of disability studies* (pp. 391-403). Routledge.

Smith, B. *et al.* (2021). Disability, the communication of physical activity and sedentary behaviour, and ableism: a call for inclusive messages. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*.

Smith, L. *et al.* (2015). Sport in the lives of young people with intellectual disabilities: Negotiating disability, identity and belonging.

Sparkes, A. C. and Smith, B. (2014) *Qualitative research methods in sport, exercise and health : from process to product*. Abingdon ; New York: Routledge.

Sparkes, A.C. and Smith, B., 2013. *Qualitative research methods in sport, exercise and health: From process to product*. Routledge.

Sport England (2022) *Active Lives Adult Survey*. Available at: <https://www.sportengland.org/research-and-data/data/active-lives> (Accessed December 2022)

Stephens, C. *et al.* (2012). The perceived benefits and barriers of sport in spinal cord injured individuals: a qualitative study. *Disability and rehabilitation*, 34(24), pp.2061-2070.

Stochl, J. *et al.* (2019). Identifying key targets for interventions to improve psychological wellbeing: replicable results from four UK cohorts. *Psychological medicine*, 49(14), pp.2389-2396.

Suphi, M. *et al.* (2001) *Sport and People with a Disability: Aiming at Social Inclusion*. sportscotland.

Taylor, R.S. *et al.* (2019). Exercise-based rehabilitation for heart failure: Cochrane systematic review, meta-analysis, and trial sequential analysis. *JACC: Heart Failure*, 7(8), pp.691-705.

Teixeira, P.J. *et al.* (2012). Exercise, physical activity, and self-determination theory: a systematic review. *International journal of behavioral nutrition and physical activity*, 9(1), pp.1-30.

Theis, N. *et al.* (2021). The effects of COVID-19 restrictions on physical activity and mental health of children and young adults with physical and/or intellectual disabilities. *Disability and Health Journal*, 14(3), p.101064.

Townsend, R.C. *et al.* (2015). Disability sports coaching: Towards a critical understanding. *Sports coaching review*, 4(2), pp.80-98.

UK Government (2022) *Physical activity: applying All Our Health*. Available at: [https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/physical-activity-applying-all-our-health/physical-activity-applying-all-our-health#:~:text=Around%201%20in%203%20\(34,age%2C%20especially%20in%20older%20years.](https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/physical-activity-applying-all-our-health/physical-activity-applying-all-our-health#:~:text=Around%201%20in%203%20(34,age%2C%20especially%20in%20older%20years.) (Accessed December 2022)

UK Parliament (2021) *Disabled people in employment*. Available at: <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/cbp-7540/> (accessed June 2022)

UK Parliament (2022). *Obesity Statistics*. Available at: <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/sn03336/> (Accessed December 2022)

Van De Ven, L. (2008). Strategies for autonomy used by people with cervical spinal cord injury: A qualitative study. *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 30(4), pp.249-260.

van Schijndel-Speet, M. *et al.* (2014). Facilitators and barriers to physical activity as perceived by older adults with intellectual disability. *Mental Retardation*, 52(3), pp.175-186.

Veldhuijzen van Zanten *et al.* (2016). Sedentary behaviour in people with multiple sclerosis: Is it time to stand up against MS?. *Multiple Sclerosis Journal*, 22(10), pp.1250-1256.

Wareham, Y *et al.* (2017). Coaching athletes with disability: Preconceptions and reality. *Sport in Society*, 20(9), pp.1185-1202.

Westrop, S. C. *et al.* (2019) Gender differences in physical activity and sedentary behaviour in adults with intellectual disabilities: A systematic review and meta- analysis. *Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*, 32(6), pp. 1359-1374. (doi:10.1111/jar.12648)

World Health Organisation (2001) *International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF)*. Available at: <https://www.who.int/standards/classifications/international-classification-of-functioning-disability-and-health> (Accessed: May 2022)

World Health Organisation (2022b). *Ageing and Health*. Available at <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/ageing-and-health> (Accessed June 2022)

World Health Organization. (2018) *GLOBAL ACTION PLAN ON PHYSICAL ACTIVITY 2018-2030*. Available at: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/272722/9789241514187-eng.pdf> (Accessed December 2022)

World Health Organization. (2022a) *Physical Activity Fact Sheet*. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/physical-activity> (Accessed December 2022)

Wright, A. *et al.* (2019). Barriers and facilitators to physical activity participation for children with physical disability: comparing and contrasting the views of children, young people, and their clinicians. *Disability and rehabilitation*, 41(13), pp.1499-1507.

Yazicioglu, K. *et al.* (2012) Influence of adapted sports on quality of life and life satisfaction in sport participants and non-sport participants with physical disabilities. *Disability and health Journal*, 5(4), pp.249-253.

Yilmaz, A (2020). Examining the Sports Participation Motivation Levels of Physically Disabled and Hearing Impaired Athletes. *International Journal of Applied Exercise Physiology*, 9(3), pp.55-65.

Appendices

Appendix A – Questionnaire

Understanding Disability and Sport in Scotland

Thank you for your interest in this survey. The University of the West of Scotland are working with the Observatory for Sport in Scotland and are seeking to understand the factors that impact your inclusion in sport or being physically active. Whether you are a member of a sports club, are active outside of a club or even if you do not take part in any activity, we want to hear from you. This research would like to find out about your experiences, the barriers you feel you face, your motivations and anything else that might encourage or stop you from being active. By participating in this questionnaire, you are helping to increase the knowledge of these experiences for people with disabilities. Is this project ethical? This research project has gained ethical approval from the University of West of Scotland Ethics Board. Do I have to take part? No. The decision to take part is your choice and you do not have to. This survey is not part of any club or organisation so if you choose not to complete the survey, it will not stop any of your participation. What if I have questions? We are happy to answer any questions you have before you decide to take part. You can email a member of the research team before you take part and we will be happy to answer any questions you have. Can I have someone help me take part? Yes. It is important that you are comfortable taking part so you can have someone help you or can have someone complete the survey for you. Who can help me take part or who can take part for me? It is important that the person helping you or completing the survey for you is a close relative such as a parent or adult sibling or a person who has relevant decision making powers for you which can include a legal guardian or carer. Who can I contact with any questions? If you have any questions, please contact Gemma Lumsdaine, Post graduate research student on [REDACTED]. Alternatively, you can also contact other members of the research team on: Professor Richard Davison, Principle investigator, [REDACTED] k Dr Liz Carlin, Co-investigator and postgraduate director of studies, [REDACTED] Professor Gayle McPherson, Co- investigator; [REDACTED]

Consent statements When you have read the information, had any questions answered and have decided whether you wish to take part, please click on the statements below that apply to you. All statements must be agreed to continue.

1. A. I have read and understand the information about the research and have had the opportunity to ask questions (required)
2. B. I understand that taking part in the survey is my choice and I am free to stop at any time and do not have to give a reason for stopping (required)
3. C. I understand that once I submit my answers at the end of the survey, I cannot withdraw as my answers are confidential and will not be able to be identified (required)
4. D. I agree to take part in the research (required)

Consent provision When you have read the information, had any questions answered and have decided whether you wish to take part, please click on the statement below which is true for you

1. A. I am over 18 and am completing this survey myself
2. B. I am under 18 and am completing this survey myself
3. C. I am completing this survey on behalf of someone else

If you are under 18, it is important that a parent or guardian reads all the information so they can tell us if they are happy for you to take part. Your parent or guardian must read below and click on the statement to confirm this. I am:

1. A Parent
2. A relative with legal guardianship
3. A non-relative with legal guardianship

4. I am happy to provide consent for the person to complete the survey and will provide assistance with any questions if required.

I am:

1. A Parent
2. A relative with legal guardianship
3. A non-relative with legal guardianship

I am completing the survey because:

1. The person requires physical assistance to complete the survey but they will be providing the answers themselves (this includes assistance with reading, holding a device, selecting answers on the screen)
2. The person does not have legal capacity to make decisions on participation and I am completing it without consulting with them about their answers

This first section of the survey will ask you questions about any sport or physical activity you may have done and reasons why you do or do not take part.

Do you currently participate in sport or physical activity?

1. Yes
2. No

In the past week which days did you participate in sport or physical activity? This includes activities such as going to the gym, going for a walk/push, playing a sport. This does not include activities such as gardening and housework

1. Monday
2. Tuesday
3. Wednesday
4. Thursday
5. Friday
6. Saturday
7. Sunday

How much time did you spend doing sport/physical activity on one of those days?

Minutes	<input type="checkbox"/>

How long have you participated in sport/physical activity for?

1. Less than 6 months
2. 6 -11 months

3. 1 - 2 years
4. 3- 4 years
5. 5 years or more
6. Other _____

What term would you use to describe yourself when discussing your participation level?

1. Recreational
2. Competitive - Local level e.g. I compete in club competitions
3. Competitive - Regional level e.g. I compete for Tayside
4. Competitive - National Level e.g. I compete for Scotland
5. Competitive - International e.g. I compete for GB
6. Other (please specify) _____

Do you participate in sport/physical activity on your own or in a group?

1. On my own
2. In a group
3. Both on my own and in a group

Where do you take part in sport and/or physical activity(select all that apply)?

1. School (P.E)
2. Day Centre
3. Sports Club
4. Community Club
5. After School Club
6. At my local authorities weekly session
7. In my own home
8. Outside
9. At the gym
10. Online e.g. zoom workout
11. Other (please specify) _____

What type of sport club or session do you participate in?

1. A club or session anyone can take part in
2. A disability specialist club/session
3. Both

What sport/sports do you participate in (please tick all that apply)?

1. Wheelchair Basketball
2. Para Badminton
3. Para Athletics
4. Para Swimming
5. Wheelchair Rugby
6. Frame Running
7. Wheelchair Racing
8. Para Archery
9. Online physical activity
10. Wheelchair Tennis

11. Tennis
12. Goalball
13. Boccia
14. Football (CP football, frame football, amputee football, powerchair football)
15. Para Cycling
16. Wheelchair Curling
17. Para Bowls
18. Para Shooting
19. Para Table Tennis
20. None of the above
21. Other _____

What sport/sports do you participate in (please tick all that apply)?

1. Walking/ steady push (at least 30 minutes for recreational purposes)
2. Swimming
3. Football
4. Cycling (at least 30 minutes for recreational, health, training or competition purposes)
5. Keep Fit /Aerobics
6. Multigym use / Weight Training
7. Golf
8. Running / jogging/pushing
9. Snooker / Billiards / Pool
10. Dancing
11. Bowls
12. Online physical activity
13. None of the above
14. Other (Please Specify) _____

What sport/sports do you participate in (please tick all that apply)?

1. Walking/ steady push (at least 30 minutes for recreational purposes)
2. Swimming
3. Football
4. Cycling (at least 30 minutes for recreational, health, training or competition purposes)
5. Keep Fit /Aerobics
6. Multigym use / Weight Training
7. Golf
8. Running / jogging/pushing
9. Snooker / Billiards / Pool
10. Dancing
11. Bowls
12. Wheelchair Basketball
13. Para Badminton
14. Wheelchair Rugby
15. Race Running
16. Wheelchair Racing
17. Para Archery
18. Wheelchair Tennis
19. Para Football (CP football, amputee football, powerchair football, frame football)
20. Goalball
21. Boccia
22. Para Cycling (competitive or recreational)
23. Wheelchair Curling
24. Para Shooting

25. Para Table Tennis
26. Online physical activity
27. Para Bowls
28. Para Athletics
29. Para Swimming
30. None of the above
31. Other (please specify) _____

1. To compete
2. To meet new people
3. To win
4. To improve my physical health
5. To achieve set goals (Pb's, records, medals)
6. To improve my confidence
7. To be part of a team
8. To compete at the highest level
9. To help relieve stress
10. For fun
11. To improve my mental health
12. None of the above
13. Other (please specify) _____

Since participating in sport and physical activity have you experienced any of the following benefits (select all that apply)?

1. Improved physical health
2. Increased confidence and self esteem
3. Decreased isolation
4. A more positive self-image
5. Improved mental wellbeing
6. I haven't experienced any benefits
7. Other (please specify) _____

Have you previously been involved in sport/physical activity?

1. Yes
2. No

What were the key factors that caused you to stop participating in sport/physical activity (tick all that apply)?

1. Inaccessible facilities
2. Attitudinal limitations by others (Societal views)
3. Cost of participation, equipment etc
4. Distance to my local club
5. Lack of appropriate provision eg. no BSL interpreters
6. Concerns around losing my benefits if I am seen to be active
7. Lack of self confidence
8. Difficulties with transport
9. None of the above
10. Other (please specify) _____

What challenges have you experienced with transport, if any (please tick all that apply)?

1. There is no public transport where I live which goes to the gym, sports centre etc.
2. Attitudinal limitations by others relating to spaces (Societal views)
3. Public transport is inaccessible for me due to steps, lack of space, no talking stops
4. It isn't possible for me to get to bus stops etc as the roads and pavements don't have dropped kerbs, or adaptations at pedestrian crossings (no beeps or tactile paving)
5. I can't afford to pay for transport e.g. taxi
6. I can't go on public transport on my own and it is difficult to find someone to go with me
7. Obstructions on pavements
8. I don't have access to a car
9. I live in a rural area where public transport isn't available
10. None of the above
11. Other (please specify) _____

What are the key barriers that are preventing you from participating in sport/ physical activity? Rank each factor using the slider with 5 showing a factor has strongly impacted on your participation and 1 showing a factor has not impacted on your participation

	1. Not impacted participation	2.	3.	4.	5. Strongly impacted participation
Cost of participation and/or equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of appropriate provision	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Concerns around losing my benefits if I am seen to be active	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Low self confidence	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Difficulties with transport	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other peoples thoughts and opinions about disability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Are there any other key barriers that are preventing you from participating in sport/physical activity?

What challenges have you experienced with transport, if any? (Select all that apply)

1. There is no public transport where I live which goes to the gym, sports centre etc.
2. Public transport is inaccessible for me due to steps, lack of space, no talking stops
3. It isn't possible for me to get to bus stops etc as the roads and pavements don't have dropped kerbs, or adaptations at pedestrian crossings (no beeps or tactile paving)
4. I can't afford to pay for transport e.g. taxi

5. I can't go on public transport on my own and it is difficult to find someone to go with me
6. Obstructions on pavements
7. Others people's thoughts, actions and opinions
8. I don't have access to a car
9. I live in a rural area where public transport isn't available
10. None of the above
11. Other (please specify) _____

What changes would help more PWD participate in sport/physical activity?

1. Increased promotion of the sporting opportunities available to people with disabilities
2. Improved collaboration between organisations and sectors e.g., education and sport working together more
3. More qualified coaches who have experience working in disability sport
4. Increased number of volunteers
5. improved physical accessibility e.g. more adapted facilities, changing places toilets available etc
6. More funding for disability sport
7. More positive and realistic societal views of disability
8. Increased media representation of people with a range of disabilities participating in a variety of sports at both grass roots and elite level.
9. Greater understanding of the needs of people with a disability
10. More opportunities to participate in sport and physical activity at all levels
11. Improved accessibility eg. autism friendly venues, better understanding and awareness of disability
12. Other (please specify) _____

Support

The following section focuses on the support you receive from groups and organisations. This helps the research team to identify what support is currently available for PWD in Scotland and the impact that this has had on people's lives. This information will then help us to work with organisations to improve future support.

Have any of the following organisations supported you in your day-to-day life? (tick all that apply)

1. Scottish Disability Sport
2. Disability Equality Scotland
3. Deaf Action
4. SportScotland
5. Regional disability sport branch e.g. Disability Sport Fife, Forth Valley Disability Sport
6. UK Deaf Sport
7. Special Olympics Scotland
8. Inclusion Scotland
9. Disability charities e.g. Whizz Kidz, Capability Scotland, Guide Dogs Scotland, Share Scotland, MS Society
10. Local Disability organisations (Glasgow Disability Alliance, Aberdeen Action on Disability etc)
11. No Groups have supported me
12. Other (please specify) _____

How did you hear about these organisations (tick all that apply)?

1. Social media
2. Website
3. From a friend
4. Referred by health care professionals
5. School
6. Tv/Radio
7. Promotional materials e.g. poster
8. Publications
9. Other (please specify) _____

What type of support have they provided? (tick all that apply)

1. Information and advice on disability
2. Signposting to opportunities within employment
3. Advocacy
4. Social Support
5. Signposting to opportunities within education

6. Employment
7. Funding
8. Signposting to opportunities with sport and leisure
9. None of the above
10. Other (please specify) _____

How influential has this support been? Please select the number that represents how influential the support has been with 1 being not influential at all, and 5 being hugely influential in terms of the impact this has had on your life

	1	2	3	4	5
How influential has this support been?	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Have any of the following organisations supported you in a sporting or physical activity context? (select all that apply)

1. Scottish Disability Sport
2. UK Deaf Sport
3. Special Olympics Scotland
4. SportScotland
5. Sports Governing Bodies e.g. BasketballScotland
6. Regional disability sport branch e.g. Disability Sport Fife, Forth Valley Disability Sport
7. Active Schools
8. Local sports club
9. Local authority sports development staff
10. No organisations/groups have supported me
11. Other (please specify) _____

How did you hear about these organisations?

1. Social media

2. Website
3. From a friend
4. Referred by health care professionals
5. School
6. Tv/Radio
7. Promotional materials e.g. poster
8. Publications
9. Other (please specify) _____

What type of support have they provided(tick all that apply) ?

1. Information and advice on funding for sports equipment etc
2. Signposting to physical activity and sport opportunities

3. Employment
4. Education and training (coach education, Disability Inclusion Training, athlete workshops)
5. Performance pathway support
6. Social Support
7. Funding
8. None of the above
9. Other (Please Specify) _____

How influential has this support been? Please select the number that represents how influential the support has been with 1 being not influential at all, and 5 being hugely influential in terms of the impact this has had on your life

	1	2	3	4	5
How influential has this support been?	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Sedentary Behaviour

How many hours per day do you spend on a device (phone, ipad or gaming console) or watching t.v? This does not include time spent on devices for education or employment

Hours	<input type="checkbox"/>
-------	--------------------------

How many hours per day are you stationary (not wheeling, walking or moving)?

Hours	<input type="checkbox"/>
-------	--------------------------

Physical Function

This section focuses on physical function and aims to explore how your impairment affects you in day-to-day life. Questions will be asked about particular body parts, functions and the impact your disability/impairment has on your ability to do specific tasks.

Body Functions Using the following scale, please rate the extent of impairment on your bodily functions

0. I have no problem with this. 1. This can be a problem every now and then, but it is tolerable. I have rarely had an issue with this in the last 30 days. 2. This causes me problems half of the time and interferes with my day-to-day life. This has been an issue occasionally over the last 30 days. 3. This problem is present more than half of the time and partially disrupts my day-to-day life. This has happened frequently over the last 30 days. 4. This problem is present more than 95% of the time and completely impacts my day-to-day life every day

	0	1	2	3	4
Seeing	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Hearing	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Vestibular (inner ear/brain which controls balance and eye movements) Including balance functions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Pain	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Intellectual including dementia	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Energy and Drive Functions (appetite, motivation	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Perceptual Functions (ability to see, hear, or become aware of something through the senses).	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Language	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Emotional functions (Feelings)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Orientation (awareness of time, places and people)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Attention (ability to focus on something e.g. a task)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sleep	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Memory (remembering things)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Consciousness	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Voice (speaking)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Heart	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Blood pressure	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Blood	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Respiratory (breathing)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Immunological (allergies, hypersensitivity)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Digestion (turning food into nutrients)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Weight maintenance (staying the same weight)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Endocrine Glands (hormonal changes)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Defection (discharge of faeces)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Urination Functions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sexual Functions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Mobility of joints (how much movement is possible in the joints)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Muscle tone (muscle tightness)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Muscle Power (how much force can be produced)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Involuntary Movement (spasms etc)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Body structures This question focuses on parts of the body. For each body part we are trying to find out if there is any impairment, how severe that impairment is and how much this affects your day-to-day life. This information will help us to gain a better understanding around the impact of impairment on PWDlives. Using the following scale, please rate the extent of impairment on each of your body parts

0. I have no problem with this. 1. This can be a problem every now and then, but it is tolerable. I have rarely had an issue with this in the last 30 days. 2. This causes me problems half of the time and interferes with my day-to-day life. This has been an issue occasionally over the last 30 days. 3. This problem is present more than half of the time and partially disrupts my day-to-day life. This has happened frequently over the last 30 days. 4. This problem is present more than 95% of the time and completely impacts my day-to-day life every day

	0	1	2	3	4
Brain	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Spinal Cord/ Peripheral Nerves	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Eyes and Ears	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Structures involved in speech and voice	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Cardiovascular System (Heart)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Respiratory System (lungs/breathing)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Head and Neck	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Shoulder Region	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Arms and hands	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Legs and feet	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Pelvis	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Trunk	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Urinary System	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Reproductive System	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Digestive System	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Skin	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other	<input type="checkbox"/>				

The next set of questions explore the impact of disability and impairment more broadly.

On a scale of 0-5 how much does your disability affect your life? With 0 being my disability/impairment doesn't affect my life at all to 5 being my disability affects my life significantly

	0	1	2	3	4	5
How much does your disability affect your life?	<input type="checkbox"/>					

If you feel comfortable, please use the text box below to tell us how your disability affects your life

How does your disability affect you in day to day life (select all that apply)?

1. It makes me unable to complete day to day activities like cleaning and cooking independently
2. I struggle going to get shopping at the supermarket
3. It is difficult for me to attend hospital appointments on my own

4. I find it difficult to use public services such as public transport
5. My disability does not affect me in day-to-day life
6. None of the above
7. Other (please specify) _____

How does your disability affect you socially/emotionally (please tick all that apply)?

1. My disability/health condition affects my self confidence
2. Going out and socialising can be challenging for me
3. I feel nervous in new situations
4. I worry about what others think of me
5. It can be difficult to make new friends
6. My disability doesn't affect me socially or emotionally
7. It impacts my mental health
8. None of the above
9. Other (please specify) _____

Please select a number between 0 and 5 to show how much each of these factors influence your day to day life with 0 being this factor never impacts my life to 5 being this factor constantly impacts my life

	0	1	2	3	4	5
Fatigue	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Pain	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Anxiety	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Physical Inaccessibility (e.g. no ramps, no brail)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Mobility	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Structural inequalities such as lack of job opportunities	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Societal Perceptions e.g. people feeling sorry for people with disabilities	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Are there any other factors that affect you in day to day life?

Demographics

The final section of this questionnaire will ask for some general information about you or the person you are completing this form on behalf of.

Please select your age bracket from the options below

1. 12-15
2. 16-24
3. 25-32
4. 33- 40
5. 41-48
6. 49-55
7. 56-64
8. 65-70

What is your sex?

1. Male
2. Female
3. Prefer not to say

What region of Scotland do you live in?

1. Aberdeen City
2. Aberdeenshire
3. Angus
4. Argyll and Bute
5. Clackmannanshire
6. Dumfries and Galloway
7. Dundee City
8. East Ayrshire
9. East Dunbartonshire
10. East Lothian
11. East Renfrewshire
12. Edinburgh City
13. Falkirk
14. Fife
15. Glasgow City
16. Highlands
17. Inverclyde
18. Mid Lothian
19. Moray
20. North Ayrshire
21. North Lanarkshire
22. Orkney Islands
23. Perth and Kinross
24. Renfrewshire
25. Scottish Borders
26. Shetland Islands
27. South Ayrshire
28. South Lanarkshire
29. Stirling
30. West Dunbartonshire
31. West Lothian
32. Western Isles

33. Other (please specify) _____

Which of the following best describes your sexual orientation?

1. Heterosexual
2. Gay or Lesbian
3. Bisexual
4. Prefer not to say
5. Other _____

What religion or religious body do you belong to?

1. None
2. Church of Scotland
3. Roman Catholic
4. Other Christian
5. Hindu
6. Muslim
7. Jewish
8. Buddhist
9. Sikh
10. Pagan
11. Other _____

What is your ethnic group?

1. WHITE - Scottish, Other British, Irish, Gypsy / Traveller/Roma , Polish, Other white ethnic group
2. MIXED OR MULTIPLE ETHNIC GROUPS)
3. ASIAN, ASIAN SCOTTISH OR ASIAN BRITISH: Pakistani, Pakistani Scottish or Pakistani British Indian, Indian Scottish or Indian British Bangladeshi, Bangladeshi Scottish or Bangladeshi British Chinese, Chinese Scottish or Chinese British Other (please specify)
4. AFRICAN: African, African Scottish or African British Other
5. CARIBBEAN OR BLACK: Caribbean, Caribbean Scottish or Caribbean British [Black, Black Scottish or Black British
6. OTHER ETHNIC GROUP: Arab, Arab Scottish or Arab British , Don't know (spontaneous)
7. Other Ethnic Group (Please specify) _____
8. NA

What is the nature of your occupation?

1. Managerial/administrative e.g. Finance manager, company owner
2. Intermediate e.g. Secretary, administrator
3. Student
4. Routine Occupation e.g. bus driver, bar staff
5. Unemployed
6. Self Employed
7. Teacher/Teaching assistant
8. Other (Please Specify _____)

What is your household's total income from all sources over the last 12 months?

Household Income	<input type="checkbox"/>

What percentage of your household income is disability benefits?

Percentage	<input type="checkbox"/>

What educational qualifications have you gained?

1. Standard Grades/National 4 & 5's
2. Highers
3. Advanced Highers
4. Higher education non degree e.g. NQ HNC/HND, Vocational
5. Higher education degree: Masters, honours degree
6. None
7. Other (Please Specify) _____

What is your main mode of transport?

1. Car
2. Public transport e.g. Bus
3. Taxi
4. Walk/push
5. Cycle
6. Other (Please Specify) _____

Do you own your car through the Motability scheme?

1. Yes
2. No

Do you have a disability/long term health condition lasting or expected to last more than 12 months?

1. Yes
2. No
3. Don't Know

Which of these conditions or disabilities best describes the physical or mental health condition you have?

1. Difficulties with walking
2. Difficulties understanding and processing information
3. Difficulties with speaking
4. Arthritis

5. Diabetes
6. Mental Health Problems
7. Epilepsy
8. Heart, blood pressure or circulation problem
9. Dyslexia
10. Problems related to my arms and hands
11. Problems related to my legs and feet
12. Chest and Breathing Issues e.g. Asthma
13. Difficulty understanding spoken/written word
14. Difficulty hearing
15. Difficulty seeing

As you selected cycling earlier on in this questionnaire, would you be interested in answering another few questions specially relevant to this sport?

1. Yes
2. No

What type of cycling discipline do you participate in (Select more than one if required)?

1. Road
2. Mountain Biking
3. Track
4. BMX
5. Gravel
6. Leisure
7. Indoor/Spin
8. Other (please specify)

How would you describe your current level of cycling?

1. Complete Novice
2. Amateur Cyclist
3. Elite Athlete

How many times a week do you cycle?

1. Never
2. Once a week
3. Twice a week
4. 3 times a week
5. 4 times a week
6. 5 times a week
7. 6 times a week
8. 7 times a week

Are you part of a Scottish Cycling Club?

1. Yes
2. No

Looking at the list, tick what you enjoy about cycling?

1. Fitness
2. Being Outdoors
3. Health Benefits
4. Cycling with friends
5. It's a mode of transport
6. Racing
7. Other (Please specify)
8. NA

Which of the following do you believe is a barrier to cycling?

1. Cost
2. Availability of pilots
3. Limited cycle paths
4. Adaptable bikes
5. Cycling coaches who specialise in disabilities
6. Racing opportunities
7. Cycling Opportunities
8. Other (Please specify)

Thank you for taking part in the survey, your answers will help provide an excellent insight into the experiences of PWD when trying to access sport or physical activity. If you would be interested in taking part in a follow up interview, please provide your email address below:

When you are happy with your answers, please [click here](#) to submit and close the survey

Appendix B- Participant Email and information sheet

Hello

My name is Gemma Lumsdaine and I am a post graduate researcher at the University of the West of Scotland.

The University of the West of Scotland are working with the Observatory of Sport in Scotland on a research project which is seeking to understand the factors that impact your inclusion in sport or being physically active. Whether you are a member of a sports club, are active outside of a club or even if you do not take part in any activity, we want to hear from you. Therefore, we are asking you to complete this online survey to get a better picture of your personal experience.

Do I have to take part?

No. The decision to take part is your choice and you do not have to. This survey is not part of any club or organisation so if you choose not to complete the survey, it will not impact in any way on your current opportunities to participate.

What if I have questions?

We are happy to answer any questions you have before you decide to take part. You can click on the link below which will give you some more information or you can email the research team using the email address at the end of this invitation.

Can I have someone help me take part?

Yes. It is important that you are comfortable taking part so you can have someone help you or can have someone complete the survey for you.

To take part or to find out more information please click on the button below:

Kind regards

Gemma Lumsdaine
Postgraduate research student
University of the West of Scotland

Appendix C- Interview guide

Recreational sport participants – sport, recreation or physical activity lived experience	
<p><i>This guide provides some cues to help guide a discussion during the focus group with 6-8 other participants. This will help you think about what you may wish to tell us when considering your experiences of accessing sport, recreation or physical activity. The category column provides some ideas of topics that we'd like to hear about, however, please feel free to bring up any additional topics or experiences which you feel are relevant. In thinking about the areas for discussion we want you mainly to reflect on the pre-COVID-19 period (before March 2020).</i></p>	
<p>Physical factors (this includes the opportunities to participate as well as any barriers preventing or limiting these opportunities. We want to understand any positive or negative experiences you may have had)</p>	
<p>Information and awareness of opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prior to Covid-19 in March 2020, what opportunities existed for you to take part in sport, recreation or physical activity? • How easy was it for you to find out about recreational and club-based activities? • How did you find out about opportunities that existed? 	
<p>Transport options and adequacy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do you travel to access sport, recreational or physical activity? • How easy is it for you to get there and do you encounter any obstacles? • Do you require assistance in order to travel to access opportunities? • What would make it easier for you to take up opportunities? 	
<p>Access/quality of facilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you experience any barriers to accessing the sport, recreation or physical activity facilities or activities you want to use? • Are the facilities you access suitable for your needs? • What is the environment in and around the facility like in terms of accessibility? • Do you require any assistance to help you access facilities or activities and is that readily available? 	
<p>Staff awareness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In accessing sport, recreation or physical activity opportunities are facility staff aware of your needs? • Is it always possible for you to access opportunities when you want, or are there 	

restrictions in times when you can access them?	
Social Factors (this includes who you participate with and how important it is to be part of a group or be supported by others)	
Participation experience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you normally access sport, recreation or physical activity opportunities alone or with others? • How important is it to you to be part of a group? • What factors impact on your participation experience? 	
Inclusion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do the venues and spaces make you feel welcome? • Do you feel included? For example, that this is a place for you? 	
Psychological factors (this includes how motivated you are to participate in sport, recreation or physical activity and how it makes you feel)	
Motivation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How motivated are you to access sport, recreation or physical activity train and what affects that motivation? • What psychological benefits to you get from accessing opportunities? • Are there psychological stresses that you experience and what are they? 	
Sport specific factors (here we want to hear about experiences specific to your chosen sport, recreation or physical activity)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What sport, recreation or form of physical activity to you participate in and what factors impacted on that choice? • Have you noticed any difference in the availability of opportunities as a result of the 2014 Commonwealth Games and related investments? 	

Appendix D – Thematic Analysis table (example of initial coding)

Data Extract	Code
Question: What Benefits have you experienced as a result of taking part in Sport and physical activity?	
<p>the benefits are a lot. Obviously, physically, mentally, I think one of the biggest things to me is a sort of community. Within disability sport, also just swimming in general, like all the people I know, the coaches like, I can't imagine not having that sort of network. I think it's gonna give me the confidence to meet those friends. And it's going a somewhere I feel accepted a bit more than like, and just general, everyday sort of life.</p>	<p>1. The community aspect of disability sport brings an increased sense of belonging and supports acceptance</p>
<p>But But like, my body functions so much better than it could or even that like physiotherapy, physiotherapist expected to with the condition I have. Yeah, like community as well. But I think it's also helped me be more accepting of my body and its limitations.</p>	<p>2. Improved physical health</p>
<p>Like, even though I have MS, I don't think other than that I've ever been this healthy like that I like the running really kind of got me in gear and the knock on effects at heart as well, like, eating better, sleeping better, you know, kind of looking after yourself and kind of being deserving of that in a way. And then the other one particular for me around kind of MS in the community is that the park run group for people with MS is the most supportive ms support group I'm in</p>	<p>3. Increased desire to engage in positive health behaviours as a result of being part of a community</p>

Appendix E – overarching themes and associated sub themes

Psychological factors associated with disability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feelings of self acceptance • Changing the focus
Connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coaches and volunteers • The disabled community
Improved Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical Health • Mental Health and wellbeing